

CommuniCity

Innovative Solutions Responding to the Needs
of Cities & Communities - CommuniCity

D2.6 Ethics and Intersectional Inclusivity Framework

Funded by
the European Union

D2.6 Ethics and Intersectional Inclusivity Framework – Final version

Project acronym: **CommuniCity**

Project full title: **Innovative Solutions Responding to the Needs of Cities & Communities - CommuniCity**

Grant agreement no.: 101070325

Delivery Date:	31/07/2025
Lead Partner:	Demos Helsinki, (DH)
Editors:	Anna Björk, Kaisa Schmidt-Thomé, Mariela Urra Schiaffino, Bhuvana Sekar, Tuukka Puonti (DH)
Reviewers:	Hugo Kerschot/Margareda Campolargo (OASC), Neeltje Pavicic (AMS)
Dissemination Level:	PU
Version:	V1.0

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DOCUMENT INFO

Date and version number	Author	Comments
v0.1, 30/05/2025	Anna Björk, Kaisa Schmidt-Thomé, Mariela Urra Schiaffino, Bhuvana Sekar, Tuukka Puonti	First draft
v0.2, 15/06/2025	Neeltje Pavicic, Hugo Kerschot, Margarida Campolargo	Review comments
V1.0, 31/07/2025	Anna Björk, Kaisa Schmidt-Thomé, Mariela Urra Schiaffino, Bhuvana Sekar, Tuukka Puonti	Final version

Table of contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Background	10
2.1 Piloting as a general EU practise	10
2.2 Benchmarking of existing frameworks	13
2.3 From OrganiCity and SynchroniCity to CommuniCity	17
3. Agency	19
3.1 Agencies in piloting and CommuniCity.....	19
3.1.1 Cities: Being accountable managers and hosts.....	19
3.1.2 Solution providers: Mindful interventions	20
3.1.3 Individual participants: Curious and furious where needed	21
3.1.3 Researchers: SSH / sociotechnical piloting, but still research ethics	22
3.1.4 All agents: who decides over whom	22
3.2 On vulnerability and marginalisation	23
4. Ethical underpinnings for the framework	26
4.1 Applied research ethics	26
4.2 Responsible research and innovation	28
5. Intersectionality as an approach and practise	30
5.1 Intersectionality as a theory and method	30
5.2 Concerns, critiques and tensions	33
6. Co-creation as a practise for inclusivity	36
6.1 Participation	36
6.2 Co-design and co-creation	39
7. Technology and pilots in CommuniCity: Data Ethics	40
7.1 Ethics in the project’s piloting frame.....	40
7.2 Data ethics in lifecycle frame.....	40
7.2.1 Data Collection & Consent.....	40
7.2.2 Data Processing & Analysis.....	40

7.2.3 Data Use & Deployment41

7.2.4 Data Governance & Access Control41

7.2.5 Data Sharing & Secondary Use.....41

7.3 Summary of data ethics.....42

8. A Framework for inclusive technology piloting..... 43

8.1 Inputs from this background report43

8.2 Path from the initial framework towards the final version.....44

8.3 Final framework for inclusive piloting in smart cities47

9. Conclusions 53

BIBLIOGRAPHY 54

Executive Summary

As part of Task 2.2, the CommuniCity project developed a framework based on ethics and intersectional inclusivity, to guide community-driven innovation. **The Ethics and Intersectional Inclusivity Framework** blends social and technical dimensions to support ethical practices in open calls and pilots and draws on benchmarks of existing models and a broad range of theoretical discussions.

This means scoping ethics and inclusivity from both social and technical perspectives and focusing especially on the open call rounds and piloting within the limits of the project plan. Furthermore, intersectionality helps to develop strategies for dismantling systems of marginalisation, discrimination and oppression and claims that any solutions to the defined challenges must recognise and address the experiences of marginalised and/or vulnerable groups.

The Framework highlights the importance of recognising power dynamics, favouring co-creation with people whose lives the pilots touch upon, considering non-technological solutions and maintaining inclusive practices. It also recommends establishing mechanisms for anticipating and mitigating unintended consequences, thus ensuring that pilots promote equity, accountability, and long-term community trust.

The report consists of background notes and contexts for the key dimensions of the Framework, explaining the approach and reasoning behind the framework, and selected parts of the framework tool itself. **The full version of the [Framework is available on CommuniLab](#).** The overall end goal has been to develop a framework that promotes **ethical and inclusive piloting in the EU beyond the project's timeline**. Our assumption behind this task is that while corresponding and complementary frameworks do exist, the need remains for a framework that synthesizes the three angles of ethics, intersectionality and inclusivity.

In comparison with the initial Framework published in October 2023, the final version targets cities more explicitly. It suggests a way for realising inclusivity based on ethics and intersectionality as a cross-cutting dimension in the CommuniCity open call and piloting landscape. While it stands alone as a report, this framework also belongs to the series of the WP2 deliverables that complement each other.¹

¹ The series of deliverables includes the following: (D2.1 / D2.4) - Guidelines for Translating Frameworks, Methods, Tools and Principles for Local Innovations for Marginalised and Vulnerable Communities; (D2.2) A process for incremental improvement and matching needs of local citizens and communities to solutions offered by technology providers; (D2.3 / D2.7) New inclusive models for co-creation within marginalised communities and (D2.8 / D2.9) Principles of ethical and inclusive engagement. The initial version of our D2.5 Ethics and Intersectional Inclusivity Framework was delivered in October 2023, and its updated version is now published as D2.6. We remain thankful for the supportive comments and improvement suggestions given by the Ethics Board of the project as well as the project-internal reviewers of this deliverable. We tried to accommodate the feedback as far as possible.

1. Introduction

The Task 2.2 of the CommuniCity project has developed an ***ethics and intersectional inclusivity framework*** to support the project in developing an “inclusive, community-driven, agile innovation and experimentation model”. This has meant scoping ethics and inclusivity from both social and technical perspectives and focusing especially on the open call rounds and piloting within the limits of the project plan. In this context, a *framework* refers to a pre-designed structure or a set of principles that provides a foundation for a specific activity. Frameworks typically include a collection of resources and tools that can be used to simplify and accelerate a development process and offer easy ways to navigate them. Frameworks can also provide a set of recommendations and existing conventions that help the actors to avoid usual mistakes, and they can also ensure that critical questions are being addressed as part of the process.

An ***intersectional*** framework for a development process potentially increases complexity because of the added analysis of the impact, inclusivity, and representation of stakeholders in the process. An intersectional perspective refers to the requirement to consider how different forms of marginalisation – even outright exploitation and oppression in some cases – and privilege intersect and interact with each other. An intersectional approach also recognises that individuals have multiple identities that shape their experiences and highlights that different systems of marginalisation and discrimination may be interconnected. Intersectionality helps to develop strategies for dismantling these systems and claims that any solutions to challenges must recognise and address the experiences of marginalised and/or vulnerable groups.

The key concepts of the framework are the following:

Ethics - refers to a) a general approach to ethics in research and innovation, b) ethics and marginalised and / or vulnerable groups, c) ethics in the specific context of CommuniCity.

Intersectionality - refers to a specific approach to inclusive piloting as a practice, and the related ethics assessment when contextualised to marginalisation and marginalised groups. Intersectionality is conceived here as a) a key to reflecting the social, political, historical and economic realities in specific contexts; b) a research approach and methodology; c) a practice and an approach having roots in politics and social change.

Inclusivity - refers to the core principle of the project and serves as the main point of adopting the perspectives of ethics and intersectionality in piloting. Inclusivity can be considered a principle for a) participation and co-creation; b) better tech development and participatory tech design; c) innovation in general (both social- and technological innovation).

Both the co-creative identification of challenges and participation in the pilots that respond to the identified challenges should be rooted in the employment of these dimensions. Co-creation should form an integral

part of the CommuniCity piloting² and open call activities and should serve as a key tool in achieving the project’s aim to explore the potential of technological piloting for the benefit of marginalised and / or vulnerable groups. Therefore, all aspects of piloting, from challenge formation to open call to implementation to post-piloting assessments, should be considered from the perspective of practising ethics and intersectionality to reach inclusivity.

During piloting, different intentions intertwine. Several professions and communities of practice contribute to the different phases of the piloting process and bring in their own limitations and assets in terms of ethics and inclusivity. Researchers have relatively established procedures for research ethics, while designers may operate through a set of design principles. Technology developers, public sector actors and living lab operators can also have their codes of conduct – at least in the form of tacit knowledge. With all these different backgrounds and expectations coming together, it becomes obvious that a joint framework underpinning the endeavour is welcome if not a prerequisite of success. In CommuniCity, we approached this as observers that saw different “design logics” meeting and sometimes bouncing together (see the excerpt from our forthcoming article at the end of this chapter)³.

This report consists of background for the key dimensions of the framework, an explanation for the approach and reasoning behind the framework, and the framework itself. After briefly introducing existing frameworks, the report explores the key dimensions that shaped the CommuniCity framework: the agency of different actors, the ethical underpinnings, intersectionality and co-creation principles, and finally data ethics. While the initial version of the framework aimed to inform the open call and piloting activities as part of the CommuniCity project’s overall ethical considerations, the overall end goal is to propose a framework which promotes ethical and inclusive piloting in the EU beyond the project’s timeline. This is why the final framework addresses the role of cities in particular. While it has become common to refer to cities as solvers of the wicked problems of our time, one should not assume that the magic just happens. Our message is that considerable attention should be paid to the local preconditions and capabilities of cities to subscribe to the CommuniCity approach. There is much at stake in particular when engaging with the vulnerable.

² Kalender, A., Sileno, G., Ghebreab, S. (2025, forthcoming). Toward Just Smart Cities: Community-based Arts Organisations as Partners in Design Justice. CEUR Workshop Proceedings.

³ Schmidt-Thomé, K. & Björk, A. , Sekar, B. & Kalender, A. (2025, forthcoming). Applying ethics in a complex piloting context. 2025 IEEE International Symposium on Ethics in Engineering, Science, and Technology (ETHICS).

Applying ethics in a complex piloting context

Material from our Short Paper accepted for publication in the IEEE 2025 Symposium proceedings

With the increasing culture of applying piloting as part of technology innovation, the need for understanding its societal implications is becoming more crucial. In this short paper, we introduced a case in point – our CommuniCity project with technology-based piloting at its core – and explored its ethical dimensions. Drawing on a mixed-method approach, we argued that a promising avenue for refining our analysis is to scrutinize the context as a “bundle of logics”. With the aim of understanding better the power relations, tensions and agencies pivotal to negotiating and embedding ethics across processes, we identified a series of “design logics” in the data and mapped how they showed across a set of five cities.

Design logic	Ethics Contribution
Human Centered Design	Commitment to HCD to centre and engage the marginalized users directly in shaping relevant solutions
Design thinking	Adoption of design thinking framework to adjust to emerging insights during implementation in an inclusive manner
Participatory Design, Co-creation	Early engagement of the marginalized communities to ensure the consent, co-ownership, relevance and sustainability of solutions
Service Design	Service design thinking to explicate public services as ecosystems through touchpoints and experiences rather than isolated challenges.
Systems thinking	Identification of hidden interdependencies and interventions that could make or break the success of a pilot
Strategic design and policy alignment	Early engagement of policy stakeholders ensuring long-term accountability and impact more easily
Agile software development	Agile software development approaches support iterative adaptation for emerging ethical concerns through continuous feedback stages
Open innovation and cross sector collaboration	Open innovation approaches to define the public sector needs for private sector collaboration in a more transparent manner
Value sensitive design	Anticipation of explicit ethical risks upfront to develop inclusive and responsible solutions

With ethical contributions we meant the ethical affordances or potentials embedded in each design approach. There have been inherent strengths within each logic and its capacity to promote fairness, care and inclusion in how the challenges were defined, how solutions were ideated, how people were involved and if long-term thinking was leveraged. The logics can support inclusive and socially attuned pilot processes through their own “strongholds” in varying ways and degrees of success. This kind of contextual approach to ethics may be better suited to innovation piloting than relying only on top-down compliance mechanisms, especially when working with complex social issues and marginalized groups.

2. Background

2.1 Piloting as a general EU practise

Pilot based projects can be a powerful tool for improving quality of life in urban communities and fostering collaboration and innovation among community members. The EU uses piloting to implement and test policies and initiatives before their widespread adoption. Assessing their feasibility, effectiveness and potential impact in a small-scale environment enables the EU to both find promising seeds for scalable solutions and to identify potential challenges that need further consideration. Additionally, piloting allows for stakeholder feedback and input, which helps to ensure that policies are designed and implemented in a way that meets the needs and expectations of those affected by them.

To redeem these promises, piloting must have a sound processual basis. This report and the finalised framework approach the processual aspects from a particular perspective. In its finalised form, this work critically assesses which aspects we ought to consider in order to realize “an inclusive, community-driven, agile innovation and experimentation model”⁴. At the same time, it maintains a critical stance on whether “pushing the frontier of community-driven innovation to the margins of society”⁵ is feasible or desirable and, under which conditions that would be attainable.

The EU innovation policy states that: “Innovation plays an increasingly important role in our economy. As well as benefiting the EU’s consumers and workers, it is essential to creating better jobs, building a greener society, and improving our quality of life. It is also key to maintaining the EU’s competitiveness on global markets. Innovation policy is the interface between research and technological development policy and industrial policy and aims to create a framework conducive to bringing ideas to market.”⁶

From an ethical perspective, it is important to consider who is included in the core practices of this line of policy and on which terms, when piloting is used as its key tool. Indeed, if we consider the etymological roots of piloting which stem from e.g. the 16th century description of “one who steers a ship” or, in its figurative sense, “a guide, a director of the course of others”⁷, followed by successive extensions by 1848 to “one who controls a balloon” and by 1907 to “one who flies an airplane”, it is possible to further appreciate these

⁴ *Innovative Solutions Responding to the Needs of Cities & Communities | CommuniCity Project | Fact Sheet | HORIZON.* (n.d.). CORDIS | European Commission. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070325>

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ *Innovation policy | Fact Sheets on the European Union | European Parliament.* (2023, March 31). <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/67/innovation-policy>

⁷ *Pilot | Etymology, origin and meaning of pilot by etymonline.* (n.d.). <https://www.etymonline.com/word/pilot>.

connotations in its current definition in the Oxford English Dictionary as “done as an experiment or test before being introduced more widely” (Oxford English Dictionary). A pilot project could therefore be defined as a small-scale experimental project, lighting and guiding the way to broader implementation.

As central tools for innovation, pilot projects can be more than mere experiments for testing a hypothesis or trying out new ideas or methods. According to Ansell and Bartenberger⁸, pilot projects often present the logic of what they call generative experimentation, which focuses on generating new solution concepts or can act as a “proof of concept”. This type of experimentation allows the generation and continuous improvement of a proposed solution concept (such as an idea, design, policy, or program) through ongoing feedback. It is an iterative process that helps accommodate new discoveries. This can be especially beneficial for innovations aiming to influence social practices, as changes in dynamics and events can occur quickly and have a significant impact on design outcomes and modalities for implementation.

Tens of new pilot projects are run every year by the EU. They are targeted at a specific goal and designed to test the feasibility of an action or a program. They last no more than two years, and a maximum of €40 million can be annually allocated for them, according to Article 58 of the Financial Regulation⁹. It has been noted that innovation is always the story of a process¹⁰ – the process of transforming an invention (a technique, a product) or a broader solution into new practices. This process is not mechanical, however, and not every invention is transformed into an innovation. This concern for scaling up is already raised in one of the oldest proposals for a pilot project that can be found on the website of the Historical Archives of the European Union, submitted in 1975¹¹: “*The requirement to inform policy means that experiment alone is not enough - a pilot scheme must show the way to some further development. The development of future policy is the ultimate objective of the programme.*” That’s why today, several of the European Commission’s Pilot projects are turned into Preparatory Actions (PA) to prepare new EU policies, legislation and programmes. They last for up to three years and have a budget annually allocated to them, a maximum of €50 million.

However, the pilot project approach has its constraints, such as¹²:

⁸ Ansell, C. K., & Bartenberger, M. (2016). Varieties of experimentalism. *Ecological Economics*, 130, 64–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2016.05.016>

⁹ Mazur, S. (2019). *Pilot projects and preparatory actions in the annual EU budgetary procedure*, European Parliamentary Research Service.

¹⁰ Alter, N. (2010). Chapitre 1. La trajectoire des innovations. In *L’innovation ordinaire* (pp. 5–39). Presses Universitaires de France. <https://www.cairn.info/l-innovation-ordinaire--9782130583530-p-5.htm>

¹¹ European Economic Community (EEC). (1975). *Proposal for a council decision (EEC) concerning a Programme of pilot schemes and studies to combat poverty*. Available at: [https://archives.eui.eu/en/fonds/323414?item=CEUE_SEGE-01.01.01.09-COM\(1975\)0172](https://archives.eui.eu/en/fonds/323414?item=CEUE_SEGE-01.01.01.09-COM(1975)0172)

¹² Billé, R. (2010). Action without change? On the use and usefulness of pilot experiments in environmental management. *S.A.P.I.EN.S.* Available at: <http://journals.openedition.org/sapiens/979>

- (1) *“The projects have often shown their limitations in sustaining their existence from the moment the financing comes to term.*
- (2) *They don’t easily conform to the longer time scales characteristic of social change and collective action.*
- (3) *They are extremely sensitive to even small changes in local conditions (for example loss of a leader) or in the external context.*
- (4) *They contribute to the fragmentation of public action.”*

Also, the design of policy experiments is heavily influenced by the interests and attitudes of the stakeholders involved¹³. These difficulties may be duplicated at a European level, in the context of complex multi-level governance.

The concept of “pilot society” put forward by Ryghaug and Skjølvold¹⁴, triggered our interest and helped to shed critical light on the societal significance of innovation piloting. We asked, what it would mean if the paradigm of testing, iterating, and scaling technological solutions increasingly shaped the social and urban life. We started to wonder if such a future would be as progressive as piloting enthusiasts want to claim. Should it be “pushed to the margins of the society” as our project claimed to be doing, having promised to facilitate 100 tech-driven pilots across European cities? Is it (im)possible to develop a highly inclusive approach by setting principles such as the RRI to redeem the societal promises?

Rethinking Ethics and Inclusion of Urban Innovation Pilots in the ‘Pilot Society’

Material from our presentation at the STS 2025 Conference in Graz

Ryghaug and Skjølvold have made a valuable conceptual opening – the pilot society – starting to scrutinize and problematize the omnipresence of pilot activities in innovation policy. They have concluded that pilots should not be seen (and executed) narrowly as feasibility tests. While innovation pilots may inform us on which socio-technical configurations work in “real life” and have the traits that are considered desirable, they are also “political sites for the production of future socio-technical order”¹⁵. In such ‘in-between’ sites, normal obligations are often sidelined: novel technologies are given much room and accountability rules maybe loosened to get glimpses of potential technological futures. However, a ‘pilot society’, would also have to entail debates on how society intertwines with the proposed technologies and in whose interest that happens. Based on the “recent emptying of ethics within EU R&I”, Nikolova¹⁶ fears that ethics becomes construed as a means for unclogging the innovation process and embracing the collective production of

¹³ Nair, S. and Howlett, M. (2014). Design and Scaling Up of Policy Experiments and Pilots: Lessons for the Water Sector. *Lee Kuan Yew School of Public Policy Research Paper*, No. 14-35. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2535148>

¹⁴ Ryghaug, M., & Skjølvold, T. M. (2021). *Pilot Society and the Energy Transition: The co-shaping of innovation, participation and politics*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61184-2>

¹⁵ *ibid.*

¹⁶ Nikolova, B.I. (2024) From responsibility to risk: ethics in the Bermuda Triangle of EU research and innovation policy, *Science and Public Policy* 51:2, 207–217, <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad066>

risk, and that the hegemonized practices and discursive configurations would very likely stabilize the science-market alliance, excluding community-based innovation.

2.2 Benchmarking of existing frameworks

As a baseline for the CommuniCity framework’s first version, we conducted a benchmarking study to understand the landscape of frameworks intersecting the topics of ethics, technological innovation, participation and marginalised communities. Five frameworks were studied in detail, paying attention to their development process, their problem definition and its usability. No frameworks were found that fit exactly all the themes in our search criteria but all of them cover at least part of it. There are valuable learnings when studying them together. In search of examples for frameworks already in place, we looked for openly available resources with keywords such as ethics, innovation, pilots, public sector, ICT, justice, intersectionality, AI, and marginalised communities/people. For the new version of the framework, we revisited especially the Pro-Ethics Framework to see how the work had evolved, and used the reflections from the research we had conducted for our academic work (noted above). After consideration, we observed that the key points we raised from the examples for version 1 of the framework still apply for the final version as well. The five benchmarked frameworks are as follows:

1. Pro-Ethics Framework final version published in 2023¹⁷
2. Pharaon, Pilots for healthy and active ageing, Ethical guidelines, May 2020¹⁸
3. Digital Rights Governance Framework, Concept draft for feedback. Cities coalition for digital rights, UN Habitat, 2021¹⁹
4. A Framework for the Ethical Use of Advanced Data Science Methods in Humanitarian Sector, DSEG Data Science and Ethics Group, April 2020²⁰
5. European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles, European Commission, Jan 2022²¹

¹⁷ Wiarda, M., Giannelos, K., Schuerz, S., Reber, B., Doorn, N. (2023) *Ethics Framework and Guidelines: A guide for research funding organizations implementing participatory activities*. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/8089673>

¹⁸ Pharaon. *Pilots for healthy and active aging Ethical guidelines*. (2020). https://www.pharaon.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/36/2020/09/Guidelines_Ethics-Pharaon.pdf

¹⁹ [Digital Rights Framework Concept Draft.pdf](#) (2021).

²⁰ Dodgson Kate, Dr. Hirani Prithvi, Bueermann Gretchen, & Trigwell Rob. (2020). *Framework for the ethical use.pdf*. <https://www.hum-dseg.org/sites/g/files/tmzbd1476/files/2020-10/Framework%20for%20the%20ethical%20use.pdf>

²¹ Digital rights and principles. (2022). Publications Office of the European Union. *European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade*, Commission Decl. at Ch. 1, COM (2022) 28 final (Jan. 26, 2022), see also

The review of the frameworks illustrates that ethical issues concerning technological innovations have increasingly gained more visibility as the context of technology innovation have expanded. The rapid diversification of technologies regarding AI and Machine Learning and its applications in social innovation generates lots of opportunities, but there are still many gaps in understanding which ethical concerns need to be taken into consideration when designing, implementing and assessing the growing diversity of projects. Because of this much of the work done in the field seems to focus on understanding general ethical implementation of new technologies and participation of particular groups of people, for social inclusion. Another focus is on finding the balance right: providing the guidance without slowing down the pace of technological innovation.

In the following summary, key insights from the benchmarking are organised into four themes: 1) the need for guidelines, 2) objectives and assumptions of the frameworks, 3) thematic reach, and 4) the usability of the frameworks.

1) The need for guidelines

The need to generate regulation and guiding principles has been emphasised by the EU Commission that funds much of the technological innovations development in the EU. In 2022 the Commission proposed a “European declaration on digital rights and principles for the digital decade”. As a joint declaration with the European Parliament and the Council, this declaration stipulates “that EU values, as well as the rights and freedoms enshrined in the EU's legal framework, must be respected online as they are in the real world”²². This general set of principles talks to the need to guide “policy makers and companies developing digital technologies”²³ and to show “in the EU’s actions, future work, and engagement with global partners”.

The Pro-Ethics framework highlights that a common approach for addressing ethical concerns of technology development remains theoretically unconsolidated²⁴. Pro-Ethics underlines the need for developing ethical guidelines alongside the actual development of technology instead of treating ethics as an afterthought in the development process. The framework proposes that ethical concerns should actually even guide the development process and decisions of technology development. The development of technology cannot

European Commission (2022). Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles | Shaping Europe’s digital future. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-declaration-digital-rights-and-principles> published Dec 15, 2022.

²² European Council (2025). European declaration on digital rights and principles. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/european-declaration-on-digital-rights/>, read 30.6.2025

²³ European Commission (2025). Digital Rights and Principles <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/factpages/digital-rights-and-principles>, read 30.6.2025.

²⁴ Pro-Ethics Framework https://pro-ethics.eu/sites/site0229/media/downloads/pro_ethics_framework_guidelines.pdf; Wiarda, M., Giannelos, K., Schuerz, S., Reber, B., Doorn, N. (2023) *Ethics Framework and Guidelines: A guide for research funding organizations implementing participatory activities*. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/8089673>

depend on legislation alone because of the fast pace of innovation and changes in the field, but instead make use of ethical guidelines that embrace pluralism and broad perspectives. In practice, technology developers should consult professional ethical expertise and highlight responsibility as a key dimension of the development process.

Pro-Ethics points also to the increasing need for frameworks as the participatory practices are becoming increasingly common. The more technological development focuses on participation of non-traditional stakeholders, the higher is the need to pay attention to the conceptualisation of participation. For instance, in each context "participation" can refer to a wide range of involvement of participants, from merely gathering data from people to consulting opinions to actively co-creating solutions. There is even more concern when considering the participation of vulnerable sectors of the population such as children, elderly people, marginalised communities or people in need of humanitarian aid. Working along these groups often brings up specific ethical challenges that can not be addressed by broad generalisations.

DSGE's Framework for the Ethical Use of Advanced Data Science Methods in Humanitarian Sector²⁵ highlights the fact that in the context of humanitarian work the advantages offered by technology and digital data management are comparable to the risks for vulnerable individuals and organisations working with them. Risks include reputational risk, inappropriate use, uncertainty about data sources, intellectual property rights, and dependency and defence. Furthermore, the DSGE stresses that ensuring the dignity of participants should be considered a key dimension.

Pro-Ethics recognises a gap in EU regulation when trying to merge ethical considerations for R&I and participatory practices. Moreover, Pro-Ethics found little advancement being done in previous works integrating ethics and technological development with a broader understanding of participation of marginalised communities. So far examples of such integration are mainly Pharaon framework²⁶ which focuses on an specific R&I piloting process with older adults, and the DSGE which focuses on humanitarian work with extremely vulnerable people and less participatory activities with these groups.

2) Objectives and assumptions of the frameworks

Each of the consulted frameworks is designed for a specific R&I context: Pharaon for technological innovation to improve the lives of older adults, DSGE for data science research in humanitarian work, and Pro-Ethics for non-traditional stakeholder participation in innovation-related research projects. They have one or more defined user groups (e.g. researchers conducting pilots that include participation of older adults, care-takers

²⁵ Dodgson K., Prithvi, H., Bueermann G. & Trigwell, R.. (2020). *Framework for the ethical use.pdf*. <https://www.hum-dseg.org/sites/g/files/tmzbd11476/files/2020-10/Framework%20for%20the%20ethical%20use.pdf>

²⁶ Pharaon. Pilots for healthy and active aging Ethical guidelines (2020). https://www.pharaon.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/36/2020/09/Guidelines_Ethics-Pharaon.pdf

of older adults when participating in innovation pilots, researchers collecting data of extremely vulnerable people for humanitarian purposes, researchers searching to conduct pilots that includes participation of citizens). Additionally, the frameworks are solution-oriented – they offer a structured understanding of the possible ethical implications and easy-to-understand guidelines to anticipate and overcome troubles.

In general, frameworks are tools to navigate complexity of specific contexts. The framework developers thus act as complexity funnels, or translators: they offer a more approachable reading to complex issues and condense information, analysis and insights coming from different sources. They have, at the same time, much responsibility in interpreting and presenting information in an understandable manner. With this in mind, it is logical that some of the consulted frameworks don't have much use outside its specific context (e.g. Pharaon) while others expand its usability further, to the scope of the project itself (Pro-Ethics).

Frameworks are often based on some pre-set assumptions. For instance, in the Pro-Ethics and Pharaon frameworks, participation is always seen to add value (although Pro-Ethics questions this assumption at the same time). Furthermore, many frameworks are based a set of explicit principles: e.g. for Pro-Ethics the principles are fairness, transparency, equality, privacy and sustainability. The European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles also operates with principles: People at the centre; Solidarity and Inclusion; Freedom of choice; Participation; Safety and security; and Sustainability.

3) Thematic reach

The benchmarked frameworks bring together ethical considerations from a combination of themes. For instance, the themes found and recognised in DSEG's "Framework for the Ethical Use of Advanced Data Science Methods in Humanitarian Sector" are:

- Humanitarian principles and standards
- Data responsibility
- Humanitarian innovation
- AI ethics

Some frameworks treat these issues in separate sections (e.g. ethical consideration for humanitarian work, ethical considerations for data collection, ethical considerations in the deployment of AI, ethical considerations on participation of citizens, etc). This is one approach to structure the framework. Other frameworks are structured based on:

- **The user:** For instance, Pharaon structured the framework based on three user groups: Tech partners (organisations running tech innovation pilots), pilot host practitioners (e.g. care home personnel where pilots will be carried out) and researchers implementing the project.

- **Life cycle:** DSEG structures its framework around the life cycle stages of a general humanitarian data science project (Problem and solution exploration (design), data journey, algorithm, and reliance on outputs).
- **Questions:** Pro-Ethics offer a less structured alternative by guiding its context to relevant questions around the process, user and participant taxonomies.

4) The usability of the frameworks

Frameworks should be easy to approach and read. Their application is arguably as important as its content. Most of them pay special attention to the visual component. For example, there are special considerations to font size, shapes and frames, use of colours, diagrams, and visual hints. Readability increases understanding and makes them easier to navigate.

Frameworks can also be interactive, allowing the users to make different use of them according to their specific needs. Frameworks often invite to active engagement with their suggestions. They do this by offering activities, open questions, questionnaires, rating systems, tools, methods, reference to external sources, or spaces to write their own notes. Even though the frameworks are typically presented in the form of a text file, they are not designed for linear reading.

Some of these frameworks are understood as evolving documents open to feedback and reinterpretations. For example, Pro-Ethics starts from the assumption that there are not perfect formulas, but guidance is still beneficial. UN's Digital Rights Governance Framework is a draft open for feedback. Others, like Pharaon, are designed for one specific project so its usability after the end of the project is unclear. On the other hand, Pro-Ethics was designed around an iterative process of testing and reflection: a draft was first developed and tested in two rounds of piloting, after which feedback was gathered. They also contemplated feedback from actors within and outside the scope of the project for further development.

2.3 From OrganiCity and SynchroniCity to CommuniCity

The CommuniCity project applies the premises and learnings from the work of two previous consortia, who completed the projects OrganiCity (2015-2017)²⁷ and SynchroniCity (2017-2019)²⁸. The main differences between the projects are their focus groups and focus technology. Subsequently in CommuniCity, the ethics

²⁷ *OrganiCity – Co-creating smart cities of the future | OrganiCity Project | Results | H2020*. (n.d.). CORDIS | European Commission. Retrieved October 26, 2023, from <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/645198/results>

²⁸ *SynchroniCity: Delivering an IoT enabled Digital Single Market for Europe and Beyond | SynchroniCity | Project | News & Multimedia | H2020 | CORDIS | European Commission*. (n.d.). Retrieved October 26, 2023, from <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/732240/reporting>

principles from these projects are developed further to suit the principles of working with marginalised and vulnerable communities.

The CommuniCity framework for inclusive piloting (D2.6) is based on the need to analyse how to better ensure beneficial and meaningful innovation through piloting. This framework is designed for contexts that address the needs of marginalised and vulnerable groups and combines social and technological innovation as tools for responding to those needs. The overall objective of the framework is to combine the background academic and grey literature on ethics, intersectionality and inclusive co-creation with a hands-on pragmatic approach to innovation and, as a result, produce a usable framework beyond the immediate CommuniCity context.

Our assumption behind this task is that, while corresponding and complementary frameworks do exist, the need remains for a framework that synthesizes the three angles of ethics, intersectionality and inclusivity. Due to the main objectives of the project, the thematic underpinnings of our work are inspired by the academically grounded theories of critical and feminist pedagogy, sociology and political science approaches to participation and inclusivity, as well as literature in AI ethics and data justice. However, the use and documentation of academic literature in the report is limited predominantly to specific points on ethics and intersectionality. In addition, we sought to engage with the practical application of such frameworks in different contexts by drawing from the learnings of previous projects on, for instance, algorithmic biases and algorithmic discrimination, cultural inclusion and exclusion, participation and citizen engagement.

3. Agency

Running pilots to find and/or further develop citizen-centred tech solutions that focus on urban and social challenges and take also marginalised and / or vulnerable people into account, is a complex task. Such an endeavour requires multiple kinds of expertise, intensive cooperation and mutual learning in order to succeed, i.e. to be beneficial for the piloting communities and beyond. In terms of ethics and inclusivity, each contributing organisation and/or individual brings in their own **agency**, their own capabilities, aspirations and limitations. As a specific angle, we add notes on how to critically think about vulnerability and marginalisation as concepts, which are commonly and legitimately used in various contexts and project activities, but which also have implications which need to be borne in mind.

3.1 Agencies in piloting and CommuniCity

3.1.1 Cities: Being accountable managers and hosts

The managers and hosts of the piloting process are the accountable facilitators in this multi-actor cooperation. Cities as pilot managers and pilot hosts take on much of the management tasks and need to run the piloting process following the rules and regulations. On top of that their agency is central in ensuring the quality and legitimacy of the work done.

When cities act as pilot managers, like in CommuniCity, they are maneuvering in a space that goes beyond the traditional tasks and responsibilities of city administrations. Being active in piloting may tell about the willingness of a city to support the urban innovation ecosystem and the commitment to solve local challenges through piloting. Unlike most other organisations, cities can also accompany the piloting with the public interest “hat on”. As guardians of the public interest, they would thus have to be particularly mindful of potential power imbalances, to require transparency from the solution providers as well as to keep up high standards of inclusivity. At the same time, piloting represents an experimental approach that can appear risky. Novel positive things may come coupled with unpleasant surprises that may appear to work against the public interest.

Through piloting, the cities can also become facilitators of local learning processes that connect people and organisations in ways that create long-lasting collaboration also far beyond the piloting. Cities as pilot managers have the advantage of reaching out to a broad array of sector-based experts and providers of public services. However, the role of the facilitator can also prove to be demanding. In terms of ethics, an important question is who takes the blame when things do not go as well as expected. Also, in successful cases the city (or its operating arm, e.g. the local public innovation company) carries major responsibilities. Ensuring a

successful afterlife of the pilot might include public procurement that is done by the book, respecting the rules of local democracy.

To act as an accountable manager goes far beyond acting as a technical facilitator. Cities in particular cannot escape their role as guardians of the public interest. They can and must insist on high standards of transparency and inclusivity. They must also be prepared to take the blame when things do not go as well as expected and have a solid argumentation on why they chose to experiment in the first place.

3.1.2 Solution providers: Mindful interventions

The solution providers are invited to intervene in the life of the targeted cities and communities and are given the opportunity to try out if and how their solution lives up to the expectations of the piloting process. The invitation (by the call operator and the managing cities) comes with certain frame conditions which are better suited to some solution providers than to others. Even if piloting often does not include working with a high number of participants, there is in principle the opportunity for testing with large populations, which can help commercialise the piloted solutions, whereas requirements to address a highly contextual challenge can scare away providers without pre-existing local knowledge.

The solution providers take a stance – implicitly or explicitly – on several things:

- Their relationship with the **local context**: how well do they get to know the context and understand the particularities of the challenge that is addressed? If this is attempted in the first place, it matters whether the contextual knowledge is collected in advance to develop the piloted solutions or gathered along the development process.
- The **composition of the team** that develops the solution: does it incorporate individuals/experts/stakeholders from the local context? It matters a lot who is invited to shape the solution and what kind of expertise and experience are welcomed. Involving diverse people is likely to add to the quality of the solution but it might also help to deal with a situation where the challenge definition for the piloting has not been done well enough.
- The level of **engagement with the targeted communities**: how closely do the solution providers come to see what is at stake for each member or community involved in / targeted through the piloting? By serving as a living laboratory, the community sees an intervention landing in its everyday life and may experience long-standing consequences of it, unlike the solution providers that typically move on.
- Individuals as **experimental subjects**: Being ‘user-centric’ is not the same as being beneficent. If different publics are tested, monitored and influenced in experimentation, the ‘users’, or

human research subjects, may become disempowered with respect to knowledge, understanding and agency²⁹.

Ethically, the key question is how to deal with the gains and pains of piloting. An individual solution provider may often be a short-term guest in the targeted area/community and is thus not given much accountability for the intervention. If the pilot manager accepts such “rules of the game”, it must then take on the accountability. Ethical piloting means that the solution providers do not only care for the efficiency of the solution but seek to understand what the interventions mean in the targeted context. The better the pilots are rooted, the stronger conclusions about the piloted solutions they can offer. However, a good “earthing” requires that the pilot is not the centre of attention but the lives of the people.

3.1.3 Individual participants: Curious and furious where needed

The actual participants of the piloting process form potentially a very diverse group of individuals whose degree of visibility to – and influence on – what is at stake varies a lot. The pilots might frame the participants sometimes as test users and sometimes as active shapers or co-producers of the solution. Some pilots might involve an entire organisation, offering itself as a testbed and thereby giving consent on behalf of its members. In all situations, the key question is the clarity on who has given consent to what exactly. A pilot is an intervention to test whether something could work out, meaning that it may also fail. If the potential failure is not fully accounted for by the pilot manager and pilot host, or the solution provider, this can have implications for the participants. When the pilots address challenges that involve potentially vulnerable groups, it is also essential for the pilot teams to reflect all along, e.g. to understand the vulnerabilities and to avoid stigmatisation of certain individuals or groups.

The participants of the pilot – independent of their depth of involvement – have the right to be critical and to require clarity and transparency instead of becoming a passive/conform “test user only”. Often the participants are volunteering and not receiving any compensation for their efforts, so the solution providers need to plan the pilots respectfully. Participants openly sharing their views are also likely to add to the quality of the outcome, so there should be room to challenge the solution providers in any case. In a pilot, the participants may be invited to direct their attention to something that is somewhat distant to their daily lives and their ‘actual’ concerns. If the pilot needs to ‘steal’ someone’s attention and for some reason ends up having detrimental consequences for the participants, we might be talking about the abuse of the participants.

²⁹ Taylor, L. (2021). Exploitation as innovation: Research ethics and the governance of experimentation in the urban living lab. *Regional Studies*, 55(12), 1902–1912. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2020.1826421>

What comes to the ethical requirements for individual participants, it is possible to propose a certain code of conduct that all participants should adhere to in interpersonal communication. Considering the possible imbalance of stakes when dealing with vulnerable groups, the responsibility to consider things from the perspective of the others lies by the service provider and the call operator.

When engaging individuals and communities in piloting, the procedure needs to appreciate both the multiplicity of voices but also “the noises” that may arise from the living lab³⁰. As the participants are invited to be curious about an intervention, they must be allowed to be furious, too, where they feel the need. Seeing them as people with full lives instead of customers of a certain segment is the way to go.

3.1.3 Researchers: SSH / sociotechnical piloting, but still research ethics

Often piloting does not involve researchers as research is not considered necessary or possible with the available resources. When dealing with challenges of local communities, like in the case of CommuniCity pilots, researchers can prove to be very valuable both as observers and intermediaries. Their influence can be powerful in framing the piloting and in convening people to share views about their communities and the challenges they face. Such conversations can also help to improve the piloting while it is ongoing, by pointing out both bottlenecks and ways to solve them. The closer the researchers work with the community, the more delicate considerations they will face. This is where the ethical frameworks embedded in academic research practice become particularly important. Researchers typically operate under well-established ethical codes of conduct that “come with the package” of their profession. These codes emphasize principles such as informed consent, confidentiality, non-maleficence, and respect for autonomy, offering structured guidance for engaging with individuals and communities—especially those in vulnerable or marginalized positions. By default, these principles require researchers to reflect critically on the power dynamics involved in piloting, and to actively ensure that participation is meaningful rather than extractive.

Researchers need to be aware of the specific context of piloting as a multi-stakeholder, experimental context, and can utilise such tools as the Responsible Research and Innovation framework, alongside the ethical codes of conduct that are well established in the academic professions.

3.1.4 All agents: who decides over whom

Understanding the power of agenda-setting is key to ethical and inclusive piloting. Who gets to define what is at stake and around which challenges people then wrap their heads around during the actual piloting is decisive for what to expect and what to evaluate.

³⁰ See eg. Taylor, L. (2021). Exploitation as innovation: Research ethics and the governance of experimentation in the urban living lab. *Regional Studies*, 55(12), 1902–1912. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2020.1826421>

When a challenge is defined with the purpose to improve the quality of life in certain communities or to fix the service offering of a target group, the challenge definition is a very delicate matter. One has to be particularly alert if one has ended up in a situation where someone, however benevolently, decides on how to frame “their problems” without having been in touch with “them”. If reaching out to the potentially vulnerable groups is for some reason out of question, one should at least interview people who work with/for the local communities and understand the local dynamics better.

When considering the ethical implications of the power structures among agents, it is crucial to have an in-depth understanding of possible privileges included in the formation of premises of the projects, including how funding steers, limits and enables the design and implementation of the project. A consolidated process manual for both open calls and piloting enables critical assessment of possible ethical issues at early stages, and supports the flagging of generally recognised issues throughout the lifeline.

In good piloting the solution providers have a mandate from the local communities to delicately “intervene”, but those intervention(s) would have to be closely supervised by the call operators and pilot managers. Optimally, the pilot addresses a true challenge by a multi-actor team that improves the lives of a community in a way that the proposed solution can replicate.

3.2 On vulnerability and marginalisation

The introduction of new approaches and methodologies holds the promise of transforming societies for the better. Whether the innovative ideas and technologies benefit the most or just some, brings us to consider vulnerability and marginalisation. The concept of vulnerability emerged in the environmental sciences in reference to the impact of natural or economic disasters on human populations³¹. Nowadays it refers also to “a condition or state in which individuals or groups are at risk of suffering harm or discomfort”³² as vulnerability indicates “a higher probability of being hurt or harmed”. It is used to identify individuals or groups who need support with social, health or economic problems and justify their right to receive certain benefits or to gain access to services, assistance or treatment³³.

³¹ Wisner, B., & Luce, H. R. (1993). Disaster vulnerability: Scale, power and daily life. *GeoJournal*, 30(2), 127–140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00808129>

³² Anglada, M., Campo, Alba del, & Giardina, Federica. (2023). *TANDEM D1.2: PAST PROJECT REVIEW, VULNERABLE GROUPS IMPACTED BY TRANSITION POLICIES*.

³³ Virokannas, E., Liuski, S., & Kuronen, M. (2020). The contested concept of vulnerability – a literature review: Vulnerability-käsitteen kiistanalaiset merkitykset – systemaattinen kirjallisuuskatsaus : a literature review. *European Journal of Social Work*, 23(2), 327–339. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691457.2018.1508001>

Attention to vulnerability and marginalisation often comes with very good intentions. Innovation actors want to be inclusive or wish to know whether their solutions can genuinely reduce vulnerability. They may also want to consider whether certain approaches have potential repercussions on those who stand at the margins of our societies. In such situations it has become common to refer to “vulnerable groups”. For identification of such groups, three characterizations of vulnerability have been proposed³⁴: “as the product of innate/natural characteristics (innate vulnerability); as the product of past, present, or future situations and experiences (situational vulnerability); or as the product of structural characteristics and dynamics (structural vulnerability)”.

Each of the three definitions have their certain shortcomings. The innate vulnerability has been criticised for having a labelling and even stigmatising character: by counting certain groups as inherently vulnerable would necessarily be a process of othering and essentializing³⁵. One of these critics being Florencia Luna³⁶ refuses to conceive vulnerability as a “permanent and categorical condition [...] that persists throughout its existence”³⁷. Her proposal is not to think that someone is vulnerable, but to consider how a particular situation renders someone vulnerable. Instead of resembling a label, for Luna vulnerability comes in layers that may or may not actualize in different situations. The actualization has then to do with agency: the vulnerable person is one who has little choice or capacity to escape pain and injury³⁸.

In the context of piloting, we may not need definite descriptions of who is vulnerable³⁹ – or which groups are – but we may want to focus on when and where people are vulnerable and what they are vulnerable to. Which structures contribute to the vulnerability of certain people in the addressed context and related situations? Do people have the capacity to look after their own interest in these situations? Related questions include the kinds of knowledge required to identify vulnerability. Can it be done top-down based on statistics for instance, or does it require tapping into the embodied knowledge of the people whose needs are addressed – or endangered?

³⁴ Gilodi, A., Albert, I., & Nienaber, B. (2022). Vulnerability in the Context of Migration: A Critical Overview and a New Conceptual Model. *Human Arenas*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42087-022-00288-5>

³⁵ Marino, E. K., & Faas, A. J. (2020). Is Vulnerability an Outdated Concept? After Subjects and Spaces. *Annals of Anthropological Practice*, 44(1), 33–46. <https://doi.org/10.1111/napa.12132>

³⁶ Luna, F. (2009). Elucidating the Concept of Vulnerability: Layers Not Labels. *International Journal of Feminist Approaches to Bioethics*, 2(1,), 121–139.

³⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 129

³⁸ Merry, S. E. (2007). Introduction: Conditions of vulnerability. In *The Practice of Human Rights: Tracking Law Between the Global and the Local*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511819193.008>

³⁹ McLean, S. (2014). Respect for human vulnerability and personal integrity. In: ten Have, H. & Gordijn, B. (eds.), *Handbook of Global Bioethics*. Dordrecht, Springer, pp. 105–117.

In practice, the contribution of critical thinking on the concepts of vulnerability and marginalisation are complementary angles to applications of intersectionality. As researchers have noted, “...when someone occupies multiple marginalised intersections, their individual-level experiences reflect social and structural systems of power, privilege, and inequality.”⁴⁰ This means that social categories are mutually shaped by “forces” – colonialism, neoliberalism, geopolitics, etc. which shift relations of power and marginalisation⁴¹. Even though the situations of marginalised people are in principle individual, patterns exist because discrimination and marginalisation easily become systematic. For example, the dominant system of knowledge is rooted in Euro-Western frameworks. This makes it difficult to introduce and implement intersectionality frameworks in schools, academia, and policy.

In short, unitary categories in traditional diversity research tend to ignore the lived realities of the marginalised and vulnerable communities. Traditional studies and work around inclusion of marginalised people are often focused in one oppression category at the time (e.g. the poor, the immigrants, women, etc) and are studied in isolation. This approach ignores the complexity of realities and turns the oppressive systems invisible. Communities could have an active role in promoting and enabling inclusion. That could, for example, mean providing education on this issue, and paying more attention to what kinds of groupings are encouraged⁴². Furthermore, in practical contexts emphasising “marginalisation” and “vulnerability” become delicate and potentially labelling issues. Therefore, formulating challenges through co-creation, and especially when applying the joint challenges in different contexts, investing in understanding what marginalisation and vulnerability means to those contexts especially, becomes a key issue. In practice, the recruitment of participants needs to be done with careful consideration to marginalisation and vulnerability, which any categorical and essentialist thinking needs to be moved away from to avoid any stigmatisation of participants in the process.

⁴⁰ Wyatt, Tasha & Johnson, Monnique & Zaidi, Zareen. (2022). Intersectionality: a means for centering power and oppression in research. *Advances in Health Sciences Education*. 27. 10.1007/s10459-022-10110-0.

⁴¹ Dorlin, E. (2021). Beyond Intersectionality. For a Phenomenology of Domination. *Iride*, 34(3), 679-692. <https://doi.org/10.1414/103699>

⁴² Thomas, C., MacMillan, C., McKinnon, M., Torabi, H., Osmond-McLeod, M., Swavley, E., Armer, T., & Doyle, K. (2021). Seeing and Overcoming the Complexities of Intersectionality. *Challenges*, 12(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/challe12010005>

4. Ethical underpinnings for the framework

4.1 Applied research ethics

While piloting does not necessarily include research activities, in the current EU funding situation they are usually embedded in projects that include both research and innovation dimensions. Furthermore, many of the research ethics principles can be applied in designing piloting activities, as they support the explication of premises of the planned activities and help to anticipate the risk of having negative impacts on the focus groups and stakeholders. Therefore, we here discuss and apply ethics particularly as derived from applicable research ethics, and the current version of the EU’s ethics for responsible research and innovation.

Researchers themselves have noted that, when doing research with vulnerable groups, reflexivity should be the key⁴³. While the principle of ‘do no harm’ is still a valid and even an essential part of engaging with vulnerable groups in research, more sophisticated approaches have also been called for⁴⁴ to further steer for example the implementation of ethical responsibilities in e.g. social work in general, or the realisation of the principles of anti-oppressive social work⁴⁵, through ethically sound research. Practical issues with notable ethical implications such as the depositing of sensitive material⁴⁶, or the adoption of guidelines from different ethics documents have also been debated. For instance, scholars steering research with vulnerable and marginalised groups should be aware that previous reviews have found indicative discrepancy “between the acknowledged importance of the concept of vulnerability and a general understanding of the scope, content, and practical implications of vulnerability”⁴⁷. Finally, as noted above, the concept of vulnerability is a construction which imposes qualities on particular groups, and the use of which also varies across research ethics policies and guidelines⁴⁸.

⁴³ Ratnam, C., & Drozdowski, D. (2022). Research ethics with vulnerable groups: Ethics in practice and procedure. *Gender, Place & Culture*, 29(7), 1009–1030. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0966369X.2021.1994932>

⁴⁴ eg. Hugman, R., Pittaway, E., & Bartolomei, L. (2011). When “Do No Harm” Is Not Enough: The Ethics of Research with Refugees and Other Vulnerable Groups. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 41(7), 1271–1287.

⁴⁵ Pittaway, E., Bartolomei, L., & Hugman, R. (2010). “Stop Stealing Our Stories”: The Ethics of Research with Vulnerable Groups. *Journal of Human Rights Practice*, 2(2), 229–251. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhuman/huq004>

⁴⁶ Stewart, E., & Shaffer, M. (2021). The Ethical and Practical Challenges of Archiving Refugee Accounts: Reflections from Two Research Projects in the UK. *Bulletin of Sociological Methodology/Bulletin de Méthodologie Sociologique*, 150(1), 51–69. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0759106321995707>

⁴⁷ Zagorac, I. (2016). How Should We Treat the Vulnerable?: Qualitative Study of Authoritative Ethics Documents. *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved*, 27(4), 1656–1673. <https://doi.org/10.1353/hpu.2016.0154>
Shaw, R. M., Howe, J., Beazer, J., & Carr, T. (2020). Ethics and positionality in qualitative research with vulnerable and marginal groups. *Qualitative Research*, 20(3), 277–293. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794119841839>

⁴⁸ Bracken-Roche, D., Bell, E., Macdonald, M. E., & Racine, E. (2017). The concept of “vulnerability” in research ethics: An in-depth analysis of policies and guidelines. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 15(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-016-0164-6>

With the aim of giving individuals and communities agency in research projects concerning them, many researchers have chosen participatory research⁴⁹ and participatory action research⁵⁰ as their approach to data collection and analysis. This type of research has often aimed at “advocacy-focused research grounded in human rights and community participation”⁵¹, or for research accepting “that research has a role to play in supporting transformative social change”⁵². Regarding the inclusion and position of vulnerable and marginalised groups in research processes, also the institutional dimension is worth to note. First, in the context of social and technical innovation, the various practises of the governance of smart cities also generate ethical questions at different levels⁵³. Further, researchers have paid attention to the ways in which institutional principles ensure the ethical inclusion and treatment of the research participants also shape the social and cultural context where the research in question is practised⁵⁴. This also touches on the practises in use for sharing the knowledge outcomes with relevant stakeholders⁵⁵.

Innovation systems, which rely on experiments and piloting, need to be considered as posing specific questions to ethics as well. Especially when considering participatory research and e.g. participatory design in technology, humans as agents and focus groups should be considered from perspectives which reach “beyond science, technology, and competitiveness”⁵⁶. Some of the promising avenues in considering how ethics should be practised in research and innovation include (1) ex ante methods, dealing with emerging technologies, (2) intra methods, dealing with technology design, and (3) ex post methods, dealing with ethical

⁴⁹ Hugman, R., Pittaway, E., & Bartolomei, L. (2011). When “Do No Harm” Is Not Enough: The Ethics of Research with Refugees and Other Vulnerable Groups. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 41(7), 1271–1287.

⁵⁰ Pittaway, E., Bartolomei, L., & Hugman, R. (2010). “Stop Stealing Our Stories”: The Ethics of Research with Vulnerable Groups. *Journal of Human Rights Practice*, 2(2), 229–251. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhuman/huq004>

⁵¹ *ibid.*

⁵² More precisely, Gomez talks about the need to use mixed methods in research with vulnerable groups, to be able to fully address their needs. This note could be applied more broadly to designing the co-creation methodology or to challenge formation with the groups. However, methodological complexity also increases the level of complexity of possible ethical questions in general.

Gómez, A. (2014). New Developments in Mixed Methods With Vulnerable Groups. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 8(3), 317–320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689814527879>

⁵³ Ruhlandt, R. (2018). The governance of smart cities: A systematic literature review. *Cities*, 81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2018.02.014>

⁵⁴ Shaw, R. M., Howe, J., Beazer, J., & Carr, T. (2020). Ethics and positionality in qualitative research with vulnerable and marginal groups. *Qualitative Research*, 20(3), 277–293. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794119841839>

⁵⁵ Bracken-Roche, D., Bell, E., Macdonald, M. E., & Racine, E. (2017). The concept of “vulnerability” in research ethics: An in-depth analysis of policies and guidelines. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 15(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-016-0164-6>

⁵⁶ Bryden, J., & Gezelius, S. S. (2017). Innovation as if people mattered: The ethics of innovation for sustainable development. *Innovation and Development*, 7(1), 101–118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2157930X.2017.1281208>

analysis of existing technologies and uncertainties that are in place in these contexts⁵⁷. Ethical concerns across industries, e.g. when reconstructing value chains around new technologies⁵⁸ are a part of the broader image of the innovation ecosystem, but fall beyond the scope of understanding how innovation through co-creation should be developed from the ethical point of view, when dealing with marginalised groups. Further, when the context for the experiment or piloting inevitably includes multi stakeholder interaction with implicit and explicit power structures, ethical behaviour, or a general code of conduct, should be regarded as a requirement for all parties involved⁵⁹.

All in all, it has been argued that instead of linearity, we should be focusing on circular RI processes, where the whole process would be “embedded in an ethical decision-making framework for ethical innovation governance”⁶⁰. Considering the way the innovation ecosystem consists of relationships between privately owned companies and public offering and governance structures⁶¹, the ethical dimensions in considering how these innovations impact the communities and individuals they hold as their key stakeholders, should be continuously considered.

4.2 Responsible research and innovation

Ethics is one dimension of the Responsible research and innovation approach, which the European Union adopted as a focus for its R&I programmes between 2013-2020⁶². It was preceded by the development and adoption of the principles for *ethical, legal and social implications in research* (ELSI) and *ethical, legal and social aspects* (ELSA) in varying national research contexts⁶³. While the groundings for the development and groundings of these principles were laid in the international Human Genome Project (HGP) (from 1990 to 2003) by social scientists, ethics scholars and lawyers, the subsequent application of the principles under the general concept of responsible research and innovation have been mainstreamed to apply across fields and

⁵⁷ Reijers, W., Wright, D., Brey, P., Weber, K., Rodrigues, R., O’Sullivan, D., & Gordijn, B. (2018). Methods for Practising Ethics in Research and Innovation: A Literature Review, Critical Analysis and Recommendations. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 24(5), 1437–1481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-017-9961-8>

⁵⁸ Wessel, M., & Helmer, N. (2021). A Crisis of Ethics in Technology Innovation (pp. 57–70). <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/13768.003.0008>

⁵⁹ Fassin, Y. (2000). Innovation and Ethics Ethical Considerations in the Innovation Business. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 27(1), 193–203. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006427106307>

⁶⁰ Nathan, G. (2015). Innovation process and ethics in technology: An approach to ethical (responsible) innovation governance. *Journal on Chain and Network Science*, 15(2), 119–134. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JCNS2014.x018>

⁶¹ Fassin, Y. (2000). Innovation and Ethics Ethical Considerations in the Innovation Business. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 27(1), 193–203. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006427106307>

⁶² Dolan, D. D., Lee, S. S.-J., & Cho, M. K. (2022). Three decades of ethical, legal, and social implications research: Looking back to chart a path forward. *Cell Genomics*, 2(7), 100150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100150> P. 3 (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666979X22000878>)

⁶³ Ibid; see Table 2, p.3-4 for an overview

research and innovation⁶⁴. In fact, the EU had already introduced ELSA with the broad scope towards emerging sciences and technologies, stakeholder dialogues, education, and other activities as part of its 4th framework programme between 1994-1998. Along with ethics, RRI for e.g. Horizon2020 programme included public engagement, open access, gender, and science education as key themes.

In sum, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in EU contexts – or more shortly Responsible Innovation (RI) — is a policy framework and normative approach that aims to align scientific and technological advancements with societal values, needs, and expectations. It promotes inclusivity, anticipation, reflexivity, and responsiveness throughout the innovation process. All research and innovation funding through the EU mechanisms has subscribed to the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. RRI’s ethical principles have aimed for the societal desirability of the innovation process⁶⁵, favouring practices such as co-creation and transdisciplinary interaction between scientists, stakeholders, and research subjects. All this would thus apply to piloting, too. And, often a potential vehicle for advancing RRI is – piloting.

There are a number of ethics guidelines tailored to the needs of academic scholarship. They share some traits with the RRI principles but their main focus is on fostering the high standards of trustworthiness, fairness and transparency, as well as academic rigour to avoid misconduct (e.g. falsification and plagiarism and, negligence and carelessness during the research process. We presented the following guidelines in the Initial version of this Deliverable, and will thus omit them here. The initial deliverable describes the following ones in more detail:

- The Singapore Statement on Research Integrity⁶⁶
- Guidelines for the responsible conduct of research by TENK⁶⁷
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁶⁸
- Guideline for Promoting Research Integrity in Research Performing Organisations⁶⁹

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Braun, R. & Starkbaum, J. (2023). Stakeholders in Research and Innovation: Towards Responsible Governance. In: V. Blok (ed.), Putting Responsible Research and Innovation into Practice. Library of Ethics and Applied Philosophy 40, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-14710-4_12

⁶⁶ WCRIF (2022). WCRIF Singapore Statement. WCRIF - The World Conferences on Research Integrity Foundation. <https://www.wcrif.org/guidance/singapore-statement> read 30.6.2025

⁶⁷ Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (2013). Responsible conduct of research and procedures for handling allegations of misconduct in Finland.pdf. https://tenk.fi/sites/tenk.fi/files/HTK_ohje_2012.pdf

⁶⁸ ALLEA - All European Academies. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. ALLEA - All European Academies. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>

⁶⁹ SOPs4RI – Promoting excellent research. (n.d.). Retrieved October 27, 2023, from <https://sops4ri.eu/>

5. Intersectionality as an approach and practise

Ethics and intersectionality serve as building blocks to inclusivity and co-creation practises in CommuniCity. Over the past decades, intersectionality has become a significant concept in both academic, political and public discourses, and the interpretations over its meanings have diversified. This section introduces some of the basic traits of intersectionality in academia.

5.1 Intersectionality as a theory and method

Intersectionality offers a theoretical and methodological perspective to analyse and ensure inclusivity also in practice. The definitions of what intersectionality means, but the generally acknowledged origins of the approach and concept have origins in women of colour struggles in the USA and the work of Kimberley Crenshaw who describes it as “the various ways race and gender interact to shape the multiple dimensions of black women’s employment experiences”.⁷⁰ One useful approach here is the definition of intersectionality as a "conceptual and analytical framework for understanding how aspects of an individual's social and political identities combine to create different modes of discrimination and privilege"⁷¹. Furthermore, reference to the experiences of individuals in regard to the interactivity of e.g. race, class and gender in their everyday lives is at the heart of understanding the implications of applying an intersectional approach to analysis or a particular activity. In sum, intersectionality can be understood as an analytical perspective to **understand** and **transform** complex realities of social injustices (oppression, discrimination, power imbalances, privilege).

Beyond offering better understanding of social realities, intersectionality could be **understood as a tool for change**. The research⁷² claims there is one goal in the use of this concept: **justice**. Therefore, it is explicitly transformative also as an interdisciplinary field in research which analyses social phenomena and integrates previously segregated disciplines and calls for **holistic understanding**⁷³ of complex social phenomena. It analyses what the impact of social categories of identities is, when recognised by others, on the individual

⁷⁰ Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color. *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), 1241–1299. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>

⁷¹ Benkirane, S., & Doucerain, M. M. (2022). Considering intersectionality in acculturation: Bringing theory to practice. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 91, 150–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2022.10.002>

⁷² Rice, C., Harrison, E., & Friedman, M. (2019). Doing Justice to Intersectionality in Research. *Cultural Studies ↔ Critical Methodologies*, 19(6), 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708619829779>

⁷³ Gopaldas, A. (2013). Intersectionality 101. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 32(1_suppl), 90–94. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.12.044>

position and opportunities in society. It focuses both on individual hardships and oppressed groups of individuals who share similar forms of oppression and emphasises the reality of human lives as “multidimensional and complex”, where “people’s lived realities are shaped by different factors and social dynamics operating together”⁷⁴. All in all, awareness of the narratives of intersectionality allows us to think on what social mechanisms set marginalised groups apart from dominant categories. The Invisibility of these mechanisms perpetuates injustice.

To grasp the potential in – and conditions for – applying intersectionality in contemporary contexts, it is also important to pause on its origins. They can be found within black feminist debates, and other emancipatory debates on race and gender. In her ground-breaking article, Kimberley Crenshaw⁷⁵ (1991) recognised three types of intersectionality, which have been later further expanded: *structural, political and representational*. The recognition of these categories is just a first step, but the main idea is how to utilise this knowledge and understanding for finding the right mechanisms to address issues related to social discrimination.

The origins of intersectionality as a concept is based on the categories of race, gender and class as the main three identities which intersect resulting in power imbalances. Intersectionality studies have expanded over time to recognise other categories related to oppression and discrimination such as weight and marital status which are often less recognisable – i.e. naturalised (though not necessarily natural) ways of categorising population, with some of them more defined by biology, some more by social construction. This expansion is related to the evolution of the concept, away from the original social struggles of black women, even to the extent in which “newer definitions of intersectionality do not mention any particular group or social identity structures”⁷⁶. As such, the contemporary theoretical works on intersectionality deal for example with questions of how different factors and social dynamics related to oppression work together in producing

⁷⁴ Wyatt, T. R., Johnson, M., & Zaidi, Z. (2022). Intersectionality: A means for centering power and oppression in research. *Advances in Health Sciences Education: Theory and Practice*, 27(3), 863–875. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-022-10110-0>

⁷⁵ Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color. *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), 1241–1299. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>

⁷⁶ Gopaldas, A. (2013). Intersectionality 101. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 32(1_suppl), 90–94. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.12.044>

injustice and cannot therefore “be reduced to one fundamental type”⁷⁷, and how “oppression systems interlock to maintain the power and status of elites”^{78 79}.

Nowadays intersectionality has become an established concept in social sciences, as a theoretical approach and as a methodological tool. Some even claim that “intersectionality has emerged over the last decades as one of feminism’s most significant contributions to social research⁸⁰”. The European Commission is taking intersectionality approaches aligned on its commitment with gender equality, but it does not reflect in fundings and calls ([Achievements for gender equality](#)). However, it is essential for the EU to develop tools based on intersectionality to assess impacts of e.g. climate change or applications of new technologies.

Intersectionality theories do not always offer a clear set of tools for conducting social research. They point towards many different methods and methodologies, not exclusive to intersectionality studies. The concept does not offer a clear blueprint or methodology on how to conduct research. Some unresolved questions in intersectionality theories include for example “what counts as intersectional research and what criteria should determine what counts or not; how to translate the concept of intersectionality into research methods; and how many categories of differences 'race, gender, age, etc.' should be incorporated into a study?⁸¹”.

However, more than a specific or definitive research methodology, intersectionality can and should be understood as an ethical standpoint that addresses issues of power, positionality and difference. This ethical standpoint (or ethical principles) is explicitly transformative. It aims at transforming relations of power and oppression by recognizing the complexity of overarching levels of oppression. It aims at justice and ensuring the recognition of structures of oppression and privilege that remain unnamed and untheorized. It acknowledges the deep need for social transformation.

⁷⁷ Rice, C., Harrison, E., & Friedman, M. (2019). Doing Justice to Intersectionality in Research. *Cultural Studies ↔ Critical Methodologies*, 19(6), 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708619829779>

⁷⁸ Robinson, Z. (2016). *Intersectionality* (pp. 477–499). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-32250-6_23

⁷⁹ Zhang, B., Chang, B., & Du, W. (2021). Employing Intersectionality as a Data Generation Tool: Suggestions for Qualitative Researchers on Conducting Interviews of Intersectionality Study. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20, 16094069211064672. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069211064672>

⁸⁰ Rice, C., Harrison, E., & Friedman, M. (2019). Doing Justice to Intersectionality in Research. *Cultural Studies ↔ Critical Methodologies*, 19(6), 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708619829779>

⁸¹ *ibid.*

Although limitations are recognized, using intersectionality as a method can lead to emancipatory research⁸². The general aims of intersectionality research can be noted to 1) make oppression visible by recognising when, how and what social categories become relevant in power dynamics; 2) challenge the oppressions systems, by challenging the instances where supremacist perspectives are established and become invisible, and 3) giving voice to the marginalised.

From a methodological perspective, an intersectional approach includes for example a focus on gathering contextual perspectives in data collection. The aim with this is to avoid simplistic generalisations and to find compromises between simplistic generalisations and unworkable complexity⁸³, as opposed to traditional diversity research which focuses on qualitative or survey methods to examine differences across binary dimensions. Data collection following this principle aims at gathering direct perspectives from the oppressed realities, in the context in which they happen. Primary data should be gathered by on-site interviews, ethnography, participants observation, etc. Secondary data would look at historic records. Reflexivity, the examination of one's own beliefs, judgments and practices during the research process should disrupt the acts of naming others in top-down fashion. It would also place researchers in the same critical analysis as participants⁸⁴. Critical questions, such as how privilege operates in these contexts, may reveal power dynamics which, if remaining invisible, would perpetuate injustice. Different methods should aim at recognising identity categories within the specific historic and socio/cultural context studied. Categories of identities should consider community interests and the voices of the afflicted in the research design and analysis. Historical and contemporary social/cultural forces should be taken into consideration from critical perspectives⁸⁵.

5.2 Concerns, critiques and tensions

Even though the concept of intersectionality is widely recognized, many concerns exist in its application for research and beyond. These concerns are related to its effectiveness in generating the social change it claims to pursue. The extension of conceptualisation and multidisciplinary approaches can make the concept

⁸² Woodhams, C., & Lupton, B. (2014). Transformative and emancipatory potential of intersectionality research: Making a case for methodological pluralism. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 29(5), 301–307. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GM-12-2013-0139>

⁸³ Gopaldas, A. (2013). Intersectionality 101. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 32(1_suppl), 90–94. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.12.044>

⁸⁴ Rice, C., Harrison, E., & Friedman, M. (2019). Doing Justice to Intersectionality in Research. *Cultural Studies ↔ Critical Methodologies*, 19(6), 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708619829779>

⁸⁵ *ibid.*

ambiguous and confusing. It is often recognized as a challenging theory to apply⁸⁶ ⁸⁷. It is gaining much popularity, but there are concerns that the impetus on social justice can dilute the initial purposes. The use of the words has started to carry empty meaning. The main critique⁸⁸ here is that intersectionality, when used superfluously, only centres in pointing out differences. But “knowing that people occupy different social locations that afford them unique experiences is not the same as knowing how to analyse data in an intersectional way”⁸⁹.

The fact that intersectionality has gained popularity and it is currently used as an academic tool does not guarantee success in transforming patterns of inequality. Even though the hierarchies are questioned, it is not yet hinder that these structures continue to be reproduced.

Some reconceptualizations of intersectionality have extended the concept to new social issues, away from its origins, up to a point where they become unrecognisable. New reconceptualizations have ignored the struggle of women of colour, which has rendered the concept a-political⁹⁰.

Paradoxically, intersectional analysis can exclude certain categories. This may happen especially when only certain forms of exclusion/oppression are considered, experiences of privilege overshadow experiences of exclusion, or historic oppression seems to cancel out other forms of exclusion. This is exemplified⁹¹ by studies of disability when intersected with other categories, pointing to three ways in which intersectionality is incorrectly used. Intersectional categories are still categories, which reproduces what it aims to avoid. Identity coalitions single out abstract concepts of identity⁹².

There are possible directions for further understanding of use of intersectionality concepts in practice, such as for drafting intersectional policies. Intersectionality is applicable in all phases of the policy cycle:

⁸⁶ Al-Faham, H., Davis, A., & Ernst, R. (2019). Intersectionality: From Theory to Practice. *Annual Review of Law and Social Science*, 15, 247–265. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-lawsocsci-101518-042942>

⁸⁷ Gopaldas, A. (2013). Intersectionality 101. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 32(1_suppl), 90–94. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.12.044>

⁸⁸ Rice, C., Harrison, E., & Friedman, M. (2019). Doing Justice to Intersectionality in Research. *Cultural Studies ↔ Critical Methodologies*, 19(6), 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708619829779>

⁸⁹ Wyatt, T. R., Johnson, M., & Zaidi, Z. (2022). Intersectionality: A means for centering power and oppression in research. *Advances in Health Sciences Education: Theory and Practice*, 27(3), 863–875. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-022-10110-0>

⁹⁰ Rice, C., Harrison, E., & Friedman, M. (2019). Doing Justice to Intersectionality in Research. *Cultural Studies ↔ Critical Methodologies*, 19(6), 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708619829779>

⁹¹ Watermeyer, B., & Swartz, L. (2023). Disability and the problem of lazy intersectionality. *Disability & Society*, 38(2), 362–366. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2022.2130177>

⁹² Rodó-Zárate, M., & Jorba, M. (2022). Metaphors of intersectionality: Reframing the debate with a new proposal. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 29(1), 23–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350506820930734>

problematization, diagnosis, design, procedures & evaluation⁹³. In terms of vulnerable groups, the question is what the role of digital and social inclusion in vulnerable population categories (ethnic minority, elderly and pp w/disabilities) is in the paper⁹⁴ and also in ‘how to design ethical standards of inclusion in technologic innovation for elderly population’⁹⁵. In the end, for the practical application of intersectionality as an approach in piloting, its main potential seems to be situated in the contextual analysis of the piloting, assessment of the stakeholder representation throughout the project, and at the technical level, understanding and mitigating the risk of algorithmic discrimination and the exacerbation of intersectional injustices through e.g.biases in training data etc⁹⁶.

⁹³ Rodrigo, M. L. J. (2022). Políticas de igualdad de género e interseccionalidad: Estrategias y claves de articulación. *Convergencia Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 29, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.29101/crcs.v29i0.17792>

⁹⁴ Tsatsou, P. (2022). Vulnerable people’s digital inclusion: Intersectionality patterns and associated lessons. *Information, Communication & Society*, 25(10), 1475–1494. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2021.1873402>

⁹⁵ Fang, M. L. (2022). Future of AgeTech: 15th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA '22). *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments, PETRA 2022*, 536–541. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3529190.3534757>

⁹⁶ See Ojanen, A., Björk, A., Mikkonen, J., & Helsinki, D. (2022). Promoting equality in the use of Artificial Intelligence – an assessment framework for non-discriminatory AI.. Policy Brief 2022:25. Prime Minister's Office. <https://demoshelsinki.fi/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/promoting-equality-AI-2022.pdf>

6. Co-creation as a practise for inclusivity

6.1 Participation

Research and development activities are increasingly making space for participation of stakeholders, citizens and the public⁹⁷. Participation can be defined as an umbrella term encompassing a multiplicity of activities, practices and actors which connects individuals with changes. Many related terms such as dialogue, engagement, involvement, consultation are often used interchangeably as synonyms of participation. Per se participation does not indicate when, how and who does and who does not participate, nor does it define the goals or outcomes of the action of participation. Nevertheless, these questions are crucial when assessing guidelines and ethics of specific contexts. To avoid participation becoming a buzz word only, its definition should be taken seriously (e.g forms and settings of consultation are very different from those of co-creation, so are ethical implications when participants are lay citizens or individuals from marginalised groups or in situations of extreme vulnerability).

Participation can be categorised differently by considering factors such as the level of involvement, the role of participants in decision-making, or the main outcomes of the participatory process. Nevertheless, all categorisation leads to distinguishing between weak or strong forms of participation. For example, based on the level of involvement, participation can be used to refer to consultation (unidirectional, i.e. a survey), to bidirectional engagement (i.e workshops, working sessions, etc), co-creation or co-design (shared and paired involvement of participants in the development of a solution), or control (participants have more responsibilities and decision-making power than researchers). However, these four categories can be all referred to as participation.

In the context of technology innovation, participation is related to the engagement of actors, such as citizens, who would normally not be involved in the research process leading to the development of technologies. “Citizen science” is an umbrella term that can be used to refer to collaborations between scientific research and the public. Citizen science is expanding and its participatory practices are normalised nowadays⁹⁸. Examples of participatory methods used in R&D&I: citizen juries, consensus conferences, deliberative conferences, Delphi and Charette method, focus group, planning committee, scenario workshop, visions of the future, consumer workshop, global cafes, opinion polls, questionnaires, citizens advisory committee, vote

⁹⁷ See section on Research ethics and RR&I

⁹⁸ Groot, B., & Abma, T. (2022). Ethics framework for citizen science and public and patient participation in research. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 23(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-022-00761-4>

conference, interactive technology assessment, constructivist consumer TA, interdisciplinary works groups, political role play, among others.

But despite its widespread practice there are issues and unresolved frictions related to participation in innovation projects, especially when assessing ethical considerations:

“Participation is perhaps the most destabilising pillar within Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)”⁹⁹

“Despite thirty years of participatory technology assessment in Europe, issues such as “why?”, “how?” to participate and in order to reach “what quality?” are not yet solved”¹⁰⁰

Considering the multiple meanings of participation, concerns are related to its legitimacy, meaning that depending on how participation is carried out, the benefits of the engagement of external actors can be questioned. On the same note, participation does not necessarily mean that the voices of the participants will be validated and considered in decision-making processes.

The definition of the participants is another concern. The distinctions between stakeholders, citizens and individuals are blurry in innovation-related research projects. E.g. the term citizen can be used both to refer to lay individuals as representatives of civil society organisations, or stakeholder can refer to an industry as to grass-root social movements initiated by individuals. A lack of definition can lead to poor forms of participatory practices, which weakens the legitimacy of participation¹⁰¹. In the end the legitimacy of participation is not self-evident and needs to be defined in using a case-by-case approach.

Participation is usually identified as an inclusion mechanism but at the same time there is much discussion on the different forms and styles of participation, and how influential these activities are or could be. What is clear is that with no participation, there are no possibilities to bring about just decision-making processes that represent specific needs of all individuals. Then the value of participation has to do with its capacity to introduce dialogue and debate and giving the form in which these inputs influence the final outcomes.

In essence innovation can, and arguably should, serve the purpose of addressing societal needs. In R&I the unquestionable added value of involving non-traditional stakeholders, especially individuals or collective social actors, is presented as a remedy in a general context of loss of public trust which is based on the idea of participatory democracy. Participation offers the promise of bridging the existing gaps between

⁹⁹ Wiarda, M., Giannelos, K., Schuerz, S., Reber, B., Doorn, N. (2023) Ethics Framework and Guidelines: A guide for research funding organizations implementing participatory activities. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/8089673>

¹⁰⁰ *ibid.* citing Pellé & Reber 2016

¹⁰¹ *ibid.*

technology/science and society by inviting the perspectives of social actors in early stages of innovation development. It should guarantee that any social impact of new technologies and innovation is considered.

“Demands for increased public participation in policymaking have been founded upon both pragmatic and normative lines of argumentation. From a pragmatic perspective, participation is considered to improve the quality of decisions, while from a normative point of view participation is necessary to render the decision-making process more democratic”¹⁰²

In technology assessments 10 goals of participatory practices can be outlined: assessment of consequences and technical options; extension of perspective for R&D policies; agenda setting; mapping of public scientific controversies; more interactive surveys; coverage of all arguments; reframing of the debate; mediation; policy recommendations (for new technological fields); comparison of new forms of governance¹⁰³. Linkages between ethics and participation have several layers of complexity which can't easily be reduced to checklists, ticking lists and protocols. For example, the Pro-Ethics framework recognises this by stating that there might be ethical issues outside of the scope of their work, yet they still consider certain guidelines as a necessary and useful starting point.

What does participation mean for underrepresented groups of society? There are important ethical considerations in relation to the way certain groups are less represented than others if their voices are not easily reachable. For example, in the political context, while voting is seen as a genuine act of democracy, it might not be very appealing for underrepresented groups of society if their specific needs are not mentioned. Engaging in social action and community activism might thus better cater for those needs in the short run but has less influence on longer-term policymaking. Topics related to ethics and participation in citizen science are often political. Informed understanding and different perspectives are needed to break marginalisation circles or repeat stereotypes. Framing the work is necessary and requires identifying the main ethically relevant features of each situation and the exercise of placing oneself and the situation in a political and social context. This requires academic research and attentiveness¹⁰⁴.

Inclusive participation means that participatory activities would be clearly defined and adaptive enough to anticipate ethical issues in advance, in order to avoid misconduct. It means that technological innovation needs to go side by side with innovations in participatory methods to engage the ones who are less represented.

¹⁰² *ibid.*, citing Slocum, N. (2003). *Participatory Methods Toolkit: A Practitioner's Guide*. Maastricht: United Nations.

¹⁰³ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁴ Groot, B., & Abma, T. (2022). Ethics framework for citizen science and public and patient participation in research. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 23(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-022-00761-4>

6.2 Co-design and co-creation

Co-design and co-creation practices, which are at the heart of piloting at the EU level, are applications of the participation principles and discourse. *Co-design* is an approach that emphasises the involvement of various stakeholders as equal collaborators in the process of designing solutions to ensure that the outcome effectively meets their needs. In practice, examples of co-design implementation are frequently limited to the initial stages of the policy-making process. It is often described as beneficial when used in the public sector. It can help enhance idea generation, foster cooperation, and improve overall long-term outcomes and trust between citizens and public servants¹⁰⁵.

However, this approach can increase the complexity of the project and diminish control over it “because the objectives and interests of diverse people, departments or other organisations must be managed and balanced, which can require extra coordination efforts”¹⁰⁶.

Also, Blomkamp¹⁰⁷ notes that co-design initiatives can be challenging in the public sector because of the nature of the structure and culture of governments and “policy officials do not generally respond well to the risks of diminished control and increased complexity, and bureaucratic systems are not designed to be experimental or responsive”.

Co-creation on the other hand, can be seen as an alternative to co-design. This approach also seeks to make use of the knowledge and expertise of all the stakeholders to design the best solutions by involving them in the design process. Unlike co-design, however, co-creation grants stakeholders a more active role and direct involvement in the different phases of the design process, not only in the early phase. This approach contributes to a heightened sense of agency and ownership among the participants towards the project. But as well as with co-design initiatives, there is a high need to work in parallel towards a structural and cultural change in the public sector.

¹⁰⁵ Benefits of Co-design in Service Design Projects. (n.d.). International Journal of Design. Retrieved October 27, 2023, from <https://www.ijdesign.org/index.php/IJDesign/article/view/890/346>

¹⁰⁶ Steen, M. (2011). Tensions in human-centred design. *CoDesign*, 7(1), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15710882.2011.563314>

¹⁰⁷ Blomkamp, E. (2018). The Promise of Co-Design for Public Policy. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 77(4), 729–743. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12310>

7. Technology and pilots in CommuniCity: Data Ethics

7.1 Ethics in the project's piloting frame

As noted, the project design with open calls and piloting leads to a complex context for embedding ethics, because several different approaches to ethics are needed to form a full picture of the setting and possible issues. Technology, in turn, brings in especially the question of data ethics, linking to e.g. the collection of data, its storage and governance. Below, data ethics is broken down into five dimensions. The approach adopted here is based on the lifecycle approach, whereby the perspective to data ethics at different phases of the technology development is being considered.

7.2 Data ethics in lifecycle frame

7.2.1 Data Collection & Consent

One of the key issues to highlight is data governance and ownership, which has direct links to the sustainability of the pilots beyond the project timeline. Obtaining informed consent must be more than a procedural checkbox. It should be accessible and inclusive, using plain language and multiple formats suitable for individuals with disabilities. Datasets should also reflect the diversity of the communities they represent to avoid reinforcing biases. For instance, city-level data should mirror the demographics of specific districts, not just the city overall¹⁰⁸. Engaging marginalised communities in designing ethical data collection processes fosters trust and relevance.

7.2.2 Data Processing & Analysis

After data has been collected, rigorous practices are needed to guarantee ethical processing. Regular bias audits can help identify skewed representation and prevent harm to marginalised groups¹⁰⁹. Ethical MLOps and DevOps practices, emphasising accountability and continuous monitoring, form the structure of responsible machine learning development¹¹⁰.

It is recommended to implement real-time systems that flag data distribution shifts, which may indicate emerging biases. Automated fairness testing should be integrated into Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) workflows, although fairness remains a complex and context-specific metric¹¹¹. Equally, manual oversight must supplement automated processes. In cases where black-box models are used,

¹⁰⁸ <https://arxiv.org/html/2407.00170v1>

¹⁰⁹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1811.05577>

¹¹⁰ <https://helda.helsinki.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/ce998fc7-4ade-4f5c-acf9-5d7b87d16b12/content>

¹¹¹ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3238147.3238165>

explainability—through transparency around the rationale and accuracy of such systems—is important to ensure mutual understanding and agreement on their application¹¹².

7.2.3 Data Use & Deployment

Before deploying AI systems, organisations should conduct Algorithmic Impact Assessments (AIAs) to forecast potential impacts on vulnerable communities¹¹³. A structured impact assessment framework can help evaluate long-term societal consequences, such as how a model may perform amid demographic changes. In addition, organisations should prepare strict incident response protocols to manage ethical failures, outlining clear roles, points of contact, and mitigation strategies to minimise harm¹¹⁴.

7.2.4 Data Governance & Access Control

Ethical data stewardship requires clearly defined roles responsible for compliance with GDPR and broader AI ethics guidelines. Governance structures must be inclusive, featuring representation from marginalised groups to ensure diverse perspectives are considered¹¹⁵. Third-party accountability is equally important—data owners remain partially responsible even after data is shared externally. Vendors and suppliers must also adhere to the same ethical standards.

Secure data handling should follow role-based access control (RBAC) principles, restricting data access based on necessity¹¹⁶. Retention policies must be legally compliant and ethically justified, specifying clear limits on how long data is stored.

7.2.5 Data Sharing & Secondary Use

Transparency is essential when sharing data. Any conditions for sharing must be explicitly defined, ensuring that secondary uses go through an ethical review before proceeding. Community-owned data models offer an alternative framework where affected populations retain agency over how their data is used, fostering participatory governance and equitable data practices.

¹¹² <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8466590>

¹¹³ <https://ainowinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/aiareport2018.pdf>

¹¹⁴ <https://www.ethics.harvard.edu/blog/post-8-abyss-examining-ai-failures-and-lessons-learned>

¹¹⁵ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s44206-024-00101-6>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0065245808602065>

7.3 Summary of data ethics

Data collection and consent	
Intersectional Privacy Risks	Marginalised groups face higher risks of re-identification and harm. Implement differential privacy techniques and anonymisation at the point of collection Source re-identification: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666389921000143 Source differential privacy: https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-3-642-27848-8_548-1
Data Minimisation	Collect only the necessary data , especially concerning sensitive attributes (e.g., race, gender, disability, socioeconomic status). Define necessary data well and reason why it is necessary. Source: https://ainowinstitute.org/publications/data-minimization
Consent & Transparency	Make sure informed consent is obtained using accessible formats (plain language, multiple formats for disabilities).
Representative Datasets	Ensure diverse data collection to avoid reinforcing stereotypes. For example, city district data should represent the demographics of that district. Source: https://arxiv.org/html/2407.00170v1
Community Consultation	Engage marginalised groups in designing ethical data collection strategies
Data Processing & Analysis	
Bias Audits in Data Handling	Regularly assess datasets for skewed representation that could disadvantage marginalised groups Source: https://arxiv.org/abs/1811.05577
Ethical MLOps/ DevOps Practices	Real-time Flagging of Data Shifts: Implement systems that monitor data distribution changes, flagging possible biases. Automated Fairness Testing: Integrate fairness metrics (fairness is hard to quantify) into CI/CD (Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment) workflows to continuously check for biases. Manual Oversight & Explainability: Make sure human judgment is involved in critical decisions, with AI decisions made transparent to non-technical users. This is especially important with black-box systems where the models' results are not explainable. At least the reasoning for using that kind of system and accuracy measures should be provided for transparency and mutual agreement. Source: https://helda.helsinki.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/ce998fc7-4ade-4f5c-acf9-5d7b87d16b12/content
Data Use & Deployment	
Algorithmic Impact Assessments (AIAs)	Risk Forecasting: Assess potential impacts on marginalised communities before deployment. Impact Assessment Framework: Evaluate the long-term societal consequences of AI models and automated decisions. This could include forecasting demographic shifts in an area and assessing if the model works as intended during that shift. Source: https://ainowinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/aiareport2018.pdf
Incident Response Protocols	Establish clear response procedures for unintended ethical failures in AI systems. Who is in response, what is the nature of failure, how to proceed and who to contact. Minimise harm. Source: https://www.ethics.harvard.edu/blog/post-8-abyss-examining-ai-failures-and-lessons-learned
Data Governance & Access Control	
Stewardship Roles	Clearly define who is responsible for compliance with regulations like GDPR and AI ethics guidelines.
Inclusive governance	Establish ethics review boards that include representatives from marginalised groups
Third-Party Accountability	Ensure all suppliers and technology providers adhere to ethical data governance principles. In addition, if there is a failure to adhere, define responsibilities of the owner of the data and the third-parties. The data owner is never completely not responsible after sharing the data.
Secure Storage & Access Controls	Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): Limit data access to authorized personnel based on necessity. Data Retention: Define how long data is stored, ensuring compliance with legal and ethical retention guidelines.
Data Sharing & Secondary Use	
Transparency in Data Sharing	Conditions for Data Sharing → Clearly outline the circumstances under which data may be shared or disseminated. Ethical Review for Secondary Use → Require explicit ethical reviews before reusing data for purposes beyond the original intent.
Community-Owned Data Models	Consider participatory approaches where affected communities retain agency over their data.

8. A Framework for inclusive technology piloting

8.1 Inputs from this background report

The background chapter on **piloting** set the stage as it explained the central role of piloting in innovation policy and the more recent emphasis to extend piloting to tech-driven innovation with the vulnerable and/or marginalised urban communities. The scrutiny of existing ethical frameworks showed that no existing framework alone would not suffice: the CommuniCity approach would need its own framework, to enhance, for its own part, the emerging legacy of community-based innovation.

The chapter on **agency** highlighted how piloting involves a number of organisations and individuals that bring in their different capabilities, aspirations and limitations. We coined some key aspects for each kind of agency already in the first version of the Framework (in D2.4) but made them more explicit through the checklists incorporated in the final version. The sub-chapter on **vulnerability** informed especially the updated Framework as it came to emphasise the processes that precede the actual piloting in the cities, asking whether there are enough resources to cater for processes that are equitable or, even better, can help to dismantle abusive structures.

The chapter on **ethical underpinnings** focused on applying research ethics, and on the concept of Responsible Innovation (RI) in EU contexts. The RI approach aims to align scientific and technological advancements with societal values, needs, and expectations. It promotes inclusivity, anticipation, reflexivity, and responsiveness throughout the innovation process. These principles are in a key role in the Framework that we propose, but they have been phrased to pay special attention to the cities' role in particular.

The chapter on **intersectionality** introduced the concept as well as some principles for applying it in practice. In the Framework the concept of intersectionality shows as a constant call for reflection. We see that cultivating **reflection and mutual learning** should have the upper hand over attempts that try to codify very detailed guidelines. A framework attempting to have a pre-formulated advice to a maximum amount of situations (that may occur during open calls and piloting) would be too atomic and would push ethics towards a tick-the-boxes exercise.

The chapter on **co-creation** sees a central role for co-creation in practicing inclusivity and underlines that the co-creation should start already in the challenge formation phase and continue throughout the open call rounds and pilots. According to the CommuniCity principles (which were also laid out in the Framework), co-creation **for** vulnerable groups is actually no co-creation at all – it should be done **with** or even **by the vulnerable groups themselves**.

The chapter on **tech and data ethics** (added based on comments by the Ethics Board) is of somewhat different nature than the rest of this deliverable. Some of the chapter speaks more directly to the solution providers than to the cities, so its role is not very visible in the final city-oriented framework, but the key content is collected in a summary table.

8.2 Path from the initial framework towards the final version

The Ethics and Inclusivity Framework is a result of a multi-stage, reflective and co-creative process that was grounded in research, benchmarking, empirical insights, layered stakeholder engagement and iterative validation. The focus has been on ensuring that ethics, inclusivity and piloting issues converge in a practical and user-friendly framework that can be used for ethical piloting processes.

The **first draft** packaged within the D2.5 Ethics and Intersectional Inclusivity framework, encapsulated the idea that ethics and intersectionality must function as cross-cutting concerns throughout the CommuniCity piloting landscape. Rather than looking and treating ethics as optional elements, they were framed and integrated into the co-creation and evaluation by highlighting the contexts the ethical issue occurs in, what stakeholder are affected etc. The first draft was presented in a form of a summary table. Later, we modified it a bit to differentiate the issues temporally: before, during and after the pilot (see below). This draft was lightly user-tested during pilot manager (and one pilot team representative) interviews and the feedback

CommuniCity Ethics and Inclusivity Framework							
Issues	Before the Pilot (Planning, Preparation)		During the Pilot (Execution, Evaluation)			After the Pilot (Adjustment, Possible Scaling)	
	Dev	users	Hosts	researchers	XYZ	Context	Any Comments
<input type="checkbox"/> It should be considered whether there are viable alternatives to solely relying on technology-based solutions.						Underlying innovation policy and paradigm	
<input type="checkbox"/> The scale of funding must be acknowledged as it may impact the scope of offerings and the depth of co-creation opportunities, which could pose challenges.						Choosing to go for piloting	
<input type="checkbox"/> Awareness of power structures and hierarchies must be maintained in all engagements to ensure equitable participation and decision-making processes.						Choosing to go for piloting	
<input type="checkbox"/> Organizations must possess expertise in designing comprehensive processes and in training and supporting stakeholders.						Designing the open call and piloting process	
<input type="checkbox"/> The form and timing of co-creation activities should be carefully considered to ensure they align with ethical principles and address intersectionality concerns.						Designing the open call and piloting process	
<input type="checkbox"/> Exclusion criteria should be applied to approaches that are problematic in their treatment of vulnerable groups. <input type="checkbox"/> Proposals demonstrating consideration and transparency should be rewarded.						Selection criteria	
<input type="checkbox"/> Selecting the appropriate tone and vocabulary is crucial as it can significantly impact the effectiveness of communication with target audiences.						Concept and predesign	
<input type="checkbox"/> Conducting thorough contextual analysis of power structures and inequalities is essential to avoid inadvertently reinforcing them and to promote inclusivity and equity.						Concept and predesign	
<input type="checkbox"/> Understanding challenges from the perspective of vulnerable groups is optimal for effective problem definition and mitigation. <input type="checkbox"/> Involvement of city administration alone in defining challenges may lead to detachment from the context, hindering effective pilot interventions.						Challenge definition / Scoping of the pilots	
<input type="checkbox"/> Competitive settings may disadvantage less skilled developers and target groups who struggle to package their intentions effectively.						Open calls	
<input type="checkbox"/> Adherence to RR&I (Rights, Responsibilities, and Interests) and other relevant research ethics principles is essential to ensure the ethical conduct of the study and protection of all involved stakeholders. <input type="checkbox"/> Development teams should allocate time to understanding and addressing research needs to ensure ethical consideration of all stakeholders' concerns and interests.						Research	

highlighted the value of this layout, but called for clearer guidance tailored to specific stakeholder groups.

We also experimented with more holistic visualisations. One of them was a visual diagram consisting of concentric dials capturing the stakeholder roles, issue types (ethical or mitigative in nature) and the contexts. This birds-eye view made visible where and what type of ethical issues occurred as well as the density and distribution of related actors. Despite incorporating a great number of content in one image, the applicability of the complex image was found somewhat limited.

The final version pivoted from a generic piloting logic and temporal issue grouping to a city perspective, recognising that cities are the core engines and implementers in these pilots. This version organised ethical issues and concerns according to the dilemmas faced, roles and capacities of the cities, highlighting city-based participation goals, co-creation approaches, risk management, reflexivity and learning. This draft also relied on narrative-based framing and prompting questions to guide ethical reflections across the piloting landscape.

This shift to a city-based perspective was also parallely influenced by the (1) post-interview sense-making, (2) benchmarking insights from other frameworks like Pro-Ethics, Pharaon, and UN Women’s Intersectionality Framework, (3) insights on data ethics, privacy and security and finally, and (4) feedback on both the first and the fourth draft from the Ethics board which validated the approach but encouraged deeper focus on operationalisation and stakeholder feedback loops.

The final city-centric version aimed for more clarity and clearer structure. This version aims to be an adaptive, city focused and city-owned piloting reflection tool designed to evolve with the realities of complex piloting approaches demonstrated in CommuniCity. Apart from the existing issue-mapping by context and stakeholder interaction, the final framework includes a dedicated City Decision Checklist for each piloting phase. This checklist transforms the framework into a hands-on, operational tool that helps cities ask timely, strategic questions and make ethically informed decisions at every step.

The final version also explicitly incorporates pre and post pilot systemic phases (that were previously implicit), highlighting long-term considerations like ethical infrastructure, governance, and legacy planning. These additions respond directly to earlier feedback around operationalisation, accessibility, and continuity, ensuring that the framework not only supports ethical piloting but sustains it through practice, iteration, and institutional learning.

8.3 Final framework for inclusive piloting in smart cities

The final version of the framework favours **distributed ethical stewardship** instead of aiming for centralized oversight or institutional safeguarding of innovation processes. The framework recognises that **the key accountability of the CommuniCity approach lies with the cities**, as public sector organisations that subscribe to the approach. If developed further with urban communities, involving vulnerable groups, the framework could evolve even more towards community-integrated ethics stewardship.

The final version of the Framework follows five phases: (1) Setting up, (2) Before piloting, (3) During piloting, (4) After piloting, and (5) Follow-Through. It also explicates the key principles that this framework refers to. They have found their shape through the discussions with other scholars of WP2 and are aligned with the academic findings of the project.

Key Principles of CommuniCity that this framework refers to:

Co-creation with marginalised communities

CommuniCity emphasizes inclusive co-creation, particularly with communities that are often underserved, marginalised, or digitally excluded. The idea is not just to consult but to involve these communities as active co-designers in developing solutions → Enable design solutions done *with and by* them instead of *for* them.

Local needs in challenge-driven Innovation

The Open Calls of CommuniCity focus on local challenges defined by cities and communities and solved through collaborative innovation ecosystems involving SMEs, civil society and NGOs, researchers, and local government → Make sure your city is ready and willing to foster this kind of ecosystems.

Leveraging technology for inclusion

In CommuniCity, technological innovation is not seen as a goal in itself but as a tool for empowering citizens and reducing inequalities → Reflect whether emphasising the use of certain (emerging) technologies makes sense in the first place.

Each of the phases includes short descriptions of key topics that any city willing to pursue inclusive piloting needs to consider. Separate advice is given to the potential funders of such piloting schemes.

The pictures below show the phase (1) Setting up: Framing & Foundations.

Setting up <i>(Strategic Groundwork, Pre-engagement)</i>	Before the Pilot <i>(Planning, Preparation)</i>	During the Pilot <i>(Execution, Evaluation)</i>	After the Pilot <i>(Adjustment, Possible Scaling)</i>	Follow-Through <i>(Post Pilot learning, Governance, Evolution)</i>
--	---	---	---	--

Preparation Guide

Familiarisation with the CommuniCity approach; calibrating the mindset

Cities need to assess if the approach suits them in the first place: can they subscribe to it?

Sharing the ethos and the key principles
 Cities that wish to pursue the approach, must clarify their motives in advance. Interest in leveraging cutting-edge technology for urban innovation is not a wide enough as an orientation. You are also expected to care for and engage with the vulnerable and/or marginalised groups of your urban communities. You need to be ready to explore their realities and reach out to them. You must get the problem definition right and only then proceed towards finding the pilot teams. Thus, ask yourself:
Can your City adhere to the key principles of CommuniCity?

Orchestrating open calls and piloting
 Adopting the CommuniCity approach is a major commitment for any City. For cities that have little previous experience of piloting, it may be difficult to anticipate what it can mean in practice. Having decided to follow the approach, your City carries the main accountability for the series of interventions that result from the open calls. You may get some fame from successful solutions, but you need to be prepared to carry the entire blame if something goes wrong. Thus, ask:
Can your City carry the accountability for the chosen approach as a whole?

Resourcing required
 Depending on the funding you have available for your City to manage the open calls and to support the pilot teams, both time and money may prove to be limited resources. Dealing with possible problematic situations can also feel burdening. The City needs to learn a lot on the go, but it also needs to support and teach others who are new to the approach or may fail to follow key principles for other reasons. Ask:
Does your City have the available resources and skills to live up to the high expectations?

After each phase, a checklist containing questions for cities is provided. The one below corresponds with the phase (1) Framing & Foundations.

Checklist for cities

- ? Have we defined the **strategic purpose** of piloting in our city?
- ? Have we mapped our city's **participation goals and policy priorities**?
- Have we identified marginalised communities, intermediaries, and local civic actors?
- Is the **pilot team diverse** and reflective of the community it serves?
- Have we ensured **ethics is embedded** as infrastructure—not as an add-on?
- Are **funding mechanisms** flexible enough to support bottom-up engagement?
- Are benchmarking insights and existing policy frameworks informing this phase?

The next phase is (2) Before the Pilot:

Setting up <i>(Strategic Groundwork, Pre-engagement)</i>	Before the Pilot <i>(Planning, Preparation)</i>	During the Pilot <i>(Execution, Evaluation)</i>	After the Pilot <i>(Adjustment, Possible Scaling)</i>	Follow-Through <i>(Post Pilot learning, Governance, Evolution)</i>
<h2 style="margin: 0;">Preparation Guide</h2> <h3 style="margin: 0;">Ethics by design: Being considerate and thorough</h3> <p style="margin: 10px 0;"><i>Cities need to consider how they can embed the approach in the local context, to get properly rooted.</i></p> <p>Catering for access and inclusion The success of CommuniCity pilots hinges not only on the strength of the technological solutions but also on who gets to participate in shaping and implementing them. Cities must pay careful attention to the way their open calls are framed and communicated. The tone, language, and choice of dissemination channels will all affect who feels welcome to apply. Civil society organisations and NGOs can play a vital role here, not only as intermediaries between the City and marginalised groups, but also in helping applicants articulate their ideas. Yet, language skills and digital literacy can become barriers, especially in international or multilingual settings. Submission platforms and reporting portals may feel inaccessible to those with limited training or experience. Thus, Cities must ask: <i>Can we make our process accessible enough so that people with lived experience of vulnerability — not just professional developers — feel encouraged to engage?</i></p> <p>Spending time with the challenge formation One of the most significant phases in the CommuniCity journey is the careful shaping of the challenges to be addressed. If the City defines the challenges solely through the lens of its sector-based services, it risks being disconnected from lived realities. Pilots that emerge from poorly grounded problem definitions are unlikely to generate meaningful impact. Ideally, the challenge should emerge through close engagement with the affected communities — spending time with them, understanding how they see the issue, and co-defining the terms. This process may take time, involve some back and forth, and feel slower than anticipated. But without it, even the best solutions may fall flat. Ask: <i>Can your City commit to this kind of groundwork, even if the ecosystem for such engagement does not yet exist?</i></p>				

Here is the respective check-list for Phase (2).

Checklist for cities
🔍 Have we defined what inclusive success looks like for this pilot?
👉 Are co-creation activities designed to move beyond tokenism?
📁 Have we assessed ethical risks (e.g., harm, exclusion, bias)?
📄 Are informed consent , transparency, and communication plans in place?
🗣️ Are the depth and modes of participation tailored to different community needs?
🌿 Have roles and responsibilities between city staff, tech providers, and community reps been clearly set?
🔄 Are there protocols for adapting if the pilot goals shift?

Here is the Phase 3:

Setting up <i>(Strategic Groundwork, Pre-engagement)</i>	Before the Pilot <i>(Planning, Preparation)</i>	During the Pilot <i>(Execution, Evaluation)</i>	After the Pilot <i>(Adjustment, Possible Scaling)</i>	Follow-Through <i>(Post Pilot learning, Governance, Evolution)</i>
---	--	--	--	---

Preparation Guide

Ethics implemented: Being helpful, patient and critically constructive

Cities need to consider how actors with differing levels of experience can act and raise difficult questions

Giving and taking in the pilot phase

Piloting is not just about testing solutions — it is a profoundly relational process. For many community groups and less experienced applicants, the availability and responsiveness of the City team (Pilot Manager and Pilot Hosts) can make or break their journey. The City team must be ready to give: to offer guidance, make themselves available for dialogue, and help connect pilot teams with the communities they aim to serve. But the City must also be prepared to take: to uphold high expectations around ethical integrity, inclusion, and accountability. Pilots must be asked to reflect critically on their legitimacy to intervene, their respect for diverse lived experiences, and the clarity of their consent and privacy protocols. Ask:

Is your city embracing the dual role of a generous facilitator and a firm guardian of the CommuniCity approach?

Embracing reflection and navigating power

As pilots progress, they must be accompanied by a strong culture of reflection. Pilot managers, hosts, and city actors need to pay attention not only to the technical progress but to the human and relational dimensions of the work. Awareness of local power structures, hierarchies, and historical dynamics is essential — especially when working with marginalised communities. Equality impacts cannot be assessed by ticking boxes; they must be understood in context. Cities should exclude approaches that demonstrate inadequate understanding or questionable practices. At the same time, they should recognise and reward those who show openness, care, and transparency.

Can your City create an environment where this kind of critical, ethical reflection is actively encouraged?

Checklist for cities

- Are there **active feedback loops** with community participants?
- Are **power dynamics** being acknowledged and addressed in real-time?
- Are pilot facilitators trained to practice **ethical reflexivity** on the go?
- Are **data collection practices** GDPR-compliant and privacy-conscious?
- Are open conversations encouraged when tensions or concerns arise?
- Are **underrepresented groups actively shaping outcomes**—not just observing?
- Is iteration allowed, and are ethical adjustments being made mid-way?

Here are the final two phases, with a joint guide but separate checklists:

Setting up <small>(Strategic Groundwork, Pre-engagement)</small>	Before the Pilot <small>(Planning, Preparation)</small>	During the Pilot <small>(Execution, Evaluation)</small>	After the Pilot <small>(Adjustment, Possible Scaling)</small>	Follow-Through <small>(Post Pilot learning, Governance, Evolution)</small>
<h2 style="margin: 0;">Preparation Guide</h2> <h3 style="margin: 0;">Ethics evaluated, lessons learnt: Being fair and accountable</h3> <p style="margin: 10px 0;"><i>Cities need to consider how recognition is shared if outcomes are mixed or impacts uneven – and improve</i></p> <p>Sharing the fame and taking the blame As the work unfolds and outcomes begin to emerge, Cities must remain mindful of how recognition and accountability are distributed. When pilots succeed, it is essential to acknowledge all contributors — including community members, grassroots organisations, and support staff — not just the solution developers. When things go wrong, the City must be ready to take responsibility. Moreover, even so-called "successful" solutions can feel extractive if local value creation was minimal or if communities felt sidelined in the process. Recognising the effort, cherishing the empowerment of those involved, and maintaining humility even in moments of achievement — these are the hallmarks of a City that aligns with the ethos of CommuniCity. Ask yourself: <i>Can your City ensure that credit is shared fairly and that accountability is never displaced?</i></p>				

Checklist for cities

- What were the **mutual benefits** for the city and participants?
- Are **ethical and legal compliance checks** completed and documented?
- Did we evaluate the **depth and quality of participation?**
- Are outputs being translated into policy, services, or future planning?
- Has the team compiled a **reflections report** or **ethical summary?**
- Are outcomes stored with appropriate **data retention or deletion protocols?**

Checklist for cities

- What were the **mutual benefits** for the city and participants?
- Are **ethical and legal compliance checks** completed and documented?
- Did we evaluate the **depth and quality of participation?**
- Are outputs being translated into policy, services, or future planning?
- Has the team compiled a **reflections report** or **ethical summary?**
- Are outcomes stored with appropriate **data retention or deletion protocols?**

The full framework is available via CommuniLab (<https://communicity-project.eu/methodologies-tools-and-toolkits/ethical-framework/>).

Before presenting the overall conclusions, **our messages to the funding bodies** serve also as one kind of a summary of the work we have done.

When wishing to involve ‘unusual suspects’ in innovation piloting, you need to devote considerable amount of time for the preparatory phase. Please note that many pressing urban issues require other than technology-based solutions. Based on CommuniCity, an alternative route for non-tech solutions should parallel the tech-focused piloting process.

Fund grounded, inclusive, and context-aware schemes. Require prioritising of initiatives that demonstrate meaningful engagement with affected communities, thoughtful challenge definition, and clear strategies to ensure access and inclusion from the outset.

Fund pilots as ethical learning processes, not just solution tests. Require prioritising of proposals that commit to relational work, critical reflection, and ethical responsibility — especially in engagements with marginalised communities.

Fund approaches that centre shared credit and accountable practice. Support initiatives that plan for fair recognition, local value creation, and transparent responsibility.

9. Conclusions

A Framework that we developed aims to be:

- Comprehensive and evolving: The framework blends social and technical perspectives and emphasizes intersectionality and ethics throughout the piloting lifecycle.
- Ambitious and adaptable: It was designed not only for CommuniCity but with broader EU-level applicability in mind.
- Not linear but circular: It advocates for a dynamic, iterative approach to ethical innovation governance, responsive to public-private interests and community needs.
- Not control but reflection oriented: The framework nurtures critical reflection instead of trying to codify pre-defined guidelines the following of which would guarantee an ethical conduct that is “good enough”.
- Emphasis on dignity, power-awareness, and participatory methods in research ethics.

It recommends that:

- Ethics shall be an integrated process, not an afterthought.
- Co-creation with marginalised communities shall not resemble consultation but should aim for empowerment.
- Piloting should favour anticipatory and reflexive approaches that evolve with technological and societal change.
- More attention is paid to systematic ethical risk forecasting, mitigation, and feedback loops with affected communities.
- Greater institutional support is given for training and monitoring of ethical practices.

Future development needs to include:

- Data privacy and protection protocols could be more deeply embedded after they have been discussed at the programme level.
- Ethical guidelines should be living documents, with frequent revisions to keep pace with innovation.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Al-Faham, H., Davis, A., & Ernst, R. (2019). Intersectionality: From Theory to Practice. *Annual Review of Law and Social Science*, 15, 247–265. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-lawsocsci-101518-042942>
- ALLEA - All European Academies. (2023). *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*. ALLEA - All European Academies. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>
- Alter, N. (2010). Chapitre 1. La trajectoire des innovations. In *L'innovation ordinaire* (pp. 5–39). Presses Universitaires de France. <https://www.cairn.info/l-innovation-ordinaire--9782130583530-p-5.htm>
- Anglada, M., Campo, Alba del, & Giardina, Federica. (2023). *Tandem D1.2. Past project review. Vulnerable groups impacted by transition policies*. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5f9f8082a&appId=PPGMS>
- Ansell, C. K., & Bartenberger, M. (2016). Varieties of experimentalism. *Ecological Economics*, 130, 64–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2016.05.016>
- Benefits of Co-design in Service Design Projects*. (n.d.). International Journal of Design. Retrieved October 27, 2023, from <https://www.ijdesign.org/index.php/IJDesign/article/view/890/346>
- Benkirane, S., & Doucerain, M. M. (2022). Considering intersectionality in acculturation: Bringing theory to practice. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 91, 150–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2022.10.002>
- Billé, R. (2010). Action without change? On the use and usefulness of pilot experiments in environmental management. *S.A.P.I.EN.S. Surveys and Perspectives Integrating Environment and Society*, 3.1, Article 3.1. <https://journals.openedition.org/sapiens/979>
- Blomkamp, E. (2018). The Promise of Co-Design for Public Policy. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 77(4), 729–743. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12310>
- Bracken-Roche, D., Bell, E., Macdonald, M. E., & Racine, E. (2017). The concept of “vulnerability” in research ethics: An in-depth analysis of policies and guidelines. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 15(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-016-0164-6>
- Braun, R. & Starkbaum, J. (2023). Stakeholders in Research and Innovation: Towards Responsible Governance. In: V. Blok (ed.), *Putting Responsible Research and Innovation into Practice*. Library of Ethics and Applied Philosophy 40, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-14710-4_12
- Bryden, J., & Gezelius, S. S. (2017). Innovation as if people mattered: The ethics of innovation for sustainable development. *Innovation and Development*, 7(1), 101–118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2157930X.2017.1281208>
- Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color. *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), 1241–1299. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>
- Digital rights and principles*. (2022). Publications Office of the European Union. European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade, Commission Decl. at Ch. 1, COM (2022) 28 final (Jan. 26, 2022)

- Dodgson, K., Prithvi, H., Bueermann, G. & Trigwell R. (2020). *Framework for the ethical use of advanced data science methods in the humanitarian sector*. <https://www.hum-dseg.org/sites/g/files/tmzbdl1476/files/2020-10/Framework%20for%20the%20ethical%20use.pdf>
- Dolan, D. D., Lee, S. S.-J., & Cho, M. K. (2022). Three decades of ethical, legal, and social implications research: Looking back to chart a path forward. *Cell Genomics*, 2(7), 100150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100150>
- Dorlin, E. (2021). Beyond Intersectionality. For a Phenomenology of Domination. *Iride* 34(3), 679-692. <https://doi.org/10.1414/103699>
- European Commission (2022). *Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles | Shaping Europe's digital future*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-declaration-digital-rights-and-principles> published Dec 15, 2022.
- European Commission (2025). Digital Rights and Principles <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/factpages/digital-rights-and-principles>, read 30.6.2025.
- European Council (2025). *European declaration on digital rights and principles*. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/european-declaration-on-digital-rights/>, read 30.6.2025
- European Economic Community (EEC). (1975). *Proposal for a council decision (EEC) concerning a Programme of pilot schemes and studies to combat poverty*. Available at: [https://archives.eui.eu/en/fonds/323414?item=CEUE_SEGE-01.01.01.09-COM\(1975\)0172](https://archives.eui.eu/en/fonds/323414?item=CEUE_SEGE-01.01.01.09-COM(1975)0172)
- Fang, M. L. (2022). Future of AgeTech: 15th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA '22). *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments, PETRA 2022*, 536–541. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3529190.3534757>
- Fassin, Y. (2000). Innovation and Ethics Ethical Considerations in the Innovation Business. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 27(1), 193–203. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006427106307>
- Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (2013). *Responsible conduct of research and procedures for handling allegations of misconduct in Finland.pdf*. https://tenk.fi/sites/tenk.fi/files/HTK_ohje_2012.pdf
- Gilodi, A., Albert, I., & Nienaber, B. (2022). Vulnerability in the Context of Migration: A Critical Overview and a New Conceptual Model. *Human Arenas*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42087-022-00288-5>
- Gómez, A. (2014). New Developments in Mixed Methods With Vulnerable Groups. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 8(3), 317–320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689814527879>
- Gopaldas, A. (2013). Intersectionality 101. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 32(1_suppl), 90–94. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.12.044>
- Groot, B., & Abma, T. (2022). Ethics framework for citizen science and public and patient participation in research. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 23(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-022-00761-4>
- Hugman, R., Pittaway, E., & Bartolomei, L. (2011). When “Do No Harm” Is Not Enough: The Ethics of Research with Refugees and Other Vulnerable Groups. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 41(7), 1271–1287.

- Innovation policy | Fact Sheets on the European Union | European Parliament.* (2025, June 30). <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/67/innovation-policy>,
- Innovative Solutions Responding to the Needs of Cities & Communities | CommuniCity Project | Fact Sheet | HORIZON.* (n.d.). CORDIS | European Commission. Retrieved October 25, 2023, from <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070325>
- Kalender, A., Sileno, G., Ghebreab, S. (2025, forthcoming). Toward Just Smart Cities: Community-based Arts Organisations as Partners in Design Justice. CEUR Workshop Proceedings.
- Luna, F. (2009). Elucidating the Concept of Vulnerability: Layers Not Labels. *International Journal of Feminist Approaches to Bioethics*, 2(1,), 121–139.
- Marino, E. K., & Faas, A. J. (2020). Is Vulnerability an Outdated Concept? After Subjects and Spaces. *Annals of Anthropological Practice*, 44(1), 33–46. <https://doi.org/10.1111/napa.12132>
- Mazur, S. (2019). *Participatory real life experiments in research and innovation funding organisations on ethics*. 2.
- McLean, S. (2014). Respect for human vulnerability and personal integrity. In: ten Have, H. & Gordijn, B. (eds.), *Handbook of Global Bioethics*. Dordrecht, Springer, pp. 105–117.
- Merry, S. E. (2007). Introduction: Conditions of vulnerability. In *The Practice of Human Rights* (pp. 195–203). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511819193.008>
- Nair, S., & Howlett, M. P. (2014). *Design and Scaling Up of Policy Experiments and Pilots: Lessons for the Water Sector* (SSRN Scholarly Paper 2535148). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2535148>
- Nathan, G. (2015). Innovation process and ethics in technology: An approach to ethical (responsible) innovation governance. *Journal on Chain and Network Science*, 15(2), 119–134. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JCNS2014.x018>
- Nikolova, B.I. (2024) From responsibility to risk: ethics in the Bermuda Triangle of EU research and innovation policy. *Science and Public Policy* 51:2, 207–217, <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad066>
- Ojanen, A., Björk, A., Mikkonen, J., & Helsinki, D. (2002). Promoting equality in the use of Artificial Intelligence – an assessment framework for non-discriminatory AI. *Policy Brief 2022:25. Prime Minister's Office*. <https://demoshelsinki.fi/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/promoting-equality-AI-2022.pdf>
- OrganiCity – Co-creating smart cities of the future | OrganiCity Project | Results | H2020.* (n.d.). CORDIS | European Commission. Retrieved October 26, 2023, from <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/645198/results>
- Pharaon. Pilots for healthy and active aging Ethical guidelines.* (2020). https://www.pharaon.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/36/2020/09/Guidelines_Ethics-Pharaon.pdf
- Pilot | Etymology, origin and meaning of pilot by etymonline.* (n.d.). Retrieved October 26, 2023, from <https://www.etymonline.com/word/pilot>
- Pittaway, E., Bartolomei, L., & Hugman, R. (2010). “Stop Stealing Our Stories”: The Ethics of Research with Vulnerable Groups. *Journal of Human Rights Practice*, 2(2), 229–251. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhuman/huq004>

- Ratnam, C., & Drozdowski, D. (2022). Research ethics with vulnerable groups: Ethics in practice and procedure. *Gender, Place & Culture*, 29(7), 1009–1030.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0966369X.2021.1994932>
- Reijers, W., Wright, D., Brey, P., Weber, K., Rodrigues, R., O’Sullivan, D., & Gordijn, B. (2018). Methods for Practising Ethics in Research and Innovation: A Literature Review, Critical Analysis and Recommendations. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 24(5), 1437–1481.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-017-9961-8>
- Rice, C., Harrison, E., & Friedman, M. (2019). Doing Justice to Intersectionality in Research. *Cultural Studies* ↔ *Critical Methodologies*, 19(6), 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708619829779>
- Robinson, Z. (2016). *Intersectionality* (pp. 477–499). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-32250-6_23
- Rodó-Zárate, M., & Jorba, M. (2022). Metaphors of intersectionality: Reframing the debate with a new proposal. *European Journal of Women’s Studies*, 29(1), 23–38.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1350506820930734>
- Rodrigo, M. L. J. (2022). Políticas de igualdad de género e interseccionalidad: Estrategias y claves de articulación. *Convergencia Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 29, 1–24.
<https://doi.org/10.29101/crcs.v29i0.17792>
- Ruhlandt, R. (2018). The governance of smart cities: A systematic literature review. *Cities*, 81.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2018.02.014>
- Ryghaug, M., & Skjølvold, T. M. (2021). *Pilot Society and the Energy Transition: The co-shaping of innovation, participation and politics*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61184-2>
- Schmidt-Thomé, K. & Björk, A. , Sekar, B. & Kalender, A. (2025, forthcoming). Applying ethics in a complex piloting context. *2025 IEEE International Symposium on Ethics in Engineering, Science, and Technology (ETHICS)*.
- Shaw, R. M., Howe, J., Beazer, J., & Carr, T. (2020). Ethics and positionality in qualitative research with vulnerable and marginal groups. *Qualitative Research*, 20(3), 277–293.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794119841839>
- SOPs4RI – Promoting excellent research. (n.d.). Retrieved October 27, 2023, from <https://sops4ri.eu/>
- Steen, M. (2011). Tensions in human-centred design. *CoDesign*, 7(1), 45–60.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15710882.2011.563314>
- Stewart, E., & Shaffer, M. (2021). The Ethical and Practical Challenges of Archiving Refugee Accounts: Reflections from Two Research Projects in the UK. *Bulletin of Sociological Methodology/Bulletin de Méthodologie Sociologique*, 150(1), 51–69. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0759106321995707>
- SynchroniCity: Delivering an IoT enabled Digital Single Market for Europe and Beyond | SynchroniCity | Project | News & Multimedia | H2020 | CORDIS | European Commission*. (n.d.). Retrieved October 26, 2023, from <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/732240/reporting>
- Taylor, L. (2021). Exploitation as innovation: Research ethics and the governance of experimentation in the urban living lab. *Regional Studies*, 55(12), 1902–1912.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2020.1826421>

- Thomas, C., MacMillan, C., McKinnon, M., Torabi, H., Osmond-McLeod, M., Swavley, E., Armer, T., & Doyle, K. (2021). Seeing and Overcoming the Complexities of Intersectionality. *Challenges*, 12(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/challe12010005>
- Toolbox – SOPs4RI. (n.d.). Retrieved October 27, 2023, from <https://sops4ri.eu/toolbox/>
- Tsatsou, P. (2022). Vulnerable people’s digital inclusion: Intersectionality patterns and associated lessons. *Information, Communication & Society*, 25(10), 1475–1494. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2021.1873402>
- Virokannas, E., Liuski, S., & Kuronen, M. (2020). The contested concept of vulnerability – a literature review: Vulnerability-käsitteen kiistanalaiset merkitykset – systemaattinen kirjallisuuskatsaus : a literature review. *European Journal of Social Work*, 23(2), 327–339. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691457.2018.1508001>
- Watermeyer, B., & Swartz, L. (2023). Disability and the problem of lazy intersectionality. *Disability & Society*, 38(2), 362–366. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2022.2130177>
- WCRIF (2022). *WCRIF Singapore Statement*. WCRIF - The World Conferences on Research Integrity Foundation. <https://www.wcrif.org/guidance/singapore-statement> Read 30.6.2025
- Wessel, M., & Helmer, N. (2021). *A Crisis of Ethics in Technology Innovation* (pp. 57–70). <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/13768.003.0008>
- Wiarda, M., Giannelos, K., Schuerz, S., Reber, B., Doorn, N. (2023) *Ethics Framework and Guidelines: A guide for research funding organizations implementing participatory activities*. Pro-Ethics. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/8089673>
- Wisner, B., & Luce, H. R. (1993). Disaster vulnerability: Scale, power and daily life. *GeoJournal*, 30(2), 127–140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00808129>
- Woodhams, C., & Lupton, B. (2014). Transformative and emancipatory potential of intersectionality research: Making a case for methodological pluralism. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 29(5), 301–307. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GM-12-2013-0139>
- Wyatt, T. R., Johnson, M., & Zaidi, Z. (2022). Intersectionality: A means for centering power and oppression in research. *Advances in Health Sciences Education: Theory and Practice*, 27(3), 863–875. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-022-10110-0>
- Zagorac, I. (2016). How Should We Treat the Vulnerable?: Qualitative Study of Authoritative Ethics Documents. *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved*, 27(4), 1656–1673. <https://doi.org/10.1353/hpu.2016.0154>
- Zhang, B., Chang, B., & Du, W. (2021). Employing Intersectionality as a Data Generation Tool: Suggestions for Qualitative Researchers on Conducting Interviews of Intersectionality Study. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20, 16094069211064672. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069211064672>

CommuniCity